

2017

Faiths and (in) Security Conference Report

Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in
Eastleigh

Prof. Esther Mombo & Dr Wandera
St. Paul's University, Kenya
12/12/2017

Executive Summary

The Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh is a project of St. Paul's University, Limuru, Kenya. It was developed as a practical venture to complement the Master of Arts in Islam and Christian-Muslim Relations Program in 2010. The project works toward a society in which people of different faiths co-exist peacefully, creating and facilitating platforms for academic and community engagements on societal issues.

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Peace is not something you import. It is people in communities who make peace happen.

Maureen Ong'omb
St Paul's University Centre for Christian and
Muslim Relations in Eastleigh (CCRME)
Kenya

Acknowledgement

We wish to extend our gratitude to all those who made the conference a success. While there are many who contributed to the success of this important event, we wish to especially mention the following. We thank Candler School of theology through Prof. Jonathan Strom and Professor Deanna Womack for offering substantial funding towards the conference.

We also thank DanMission, Konrad Adenauer Stiftung, PROCMURA, for their support towards various aspects of the conference.

We thank Matheu Roy, First Secretary of the Canadian High Commission to Kenya for opening doors to our engagement with Canadian High Commission to Kenya, His Excellency David Angell who graced the opening of the conference. We thank Honorable Hassan, MP Kamukunji for officially opening the event.

We thank Prof. Joseph Galgalo, Vice Chancellor, St. Paul's University, the entire university management, staff and conference organizers for their support towards the event.

We thank the Masaais, who served as the communication strategists for the conference and for the participation of various media houses in the conference.

Special thanks to our hosts, the management of Jumuia County-home and Conference Centre for providing wonderful hospitality during the conference.

Finally, to the participants of the conference, 'Thank you for travelling from near and far to participate in this conference, for sharing your thoughts and ideas with us.'

'We hope this is the beginning of many more such encounters toward the development of African scholarship. We look forward to more such engagements both at home and abroad.'

ACRONYMS

BD	Bachelors of Divinity
CCMRE	Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh
CVE	Countering Violent Extremism
PROCMURA	Program for Christian-Muslim Relations in Africa
SPU	St. Paul's University, Limuru
VC	Vice Chancellor
LPI	Life &Peace Institute
ACK	Anglican Church of Kenya
WCC	World Council of Churches

Africa¹

¹<http://www.mapsofworld.com/africa/maps/africa-map.gif>

ABOUT Centre for Christian Muslim Relations in Eastleigh (CCMRE)

Institutional Identity Declaration

The CCMRE exists to provide a platform for constructive engagement between Christians-Muslims and others in Eastleigh, Nairobi, Kenya. In order to achieve this, the Center mobilizes both academic (theoretical) and practical efforts for the purposes of enabling interreligious engagement for the common good.

Vision

A society where people of different faiths peacefully and mutually co-exist

Mission

To contribute to a society where people of different faiths peacefully and mutually co-exist through creation and facilitation of platforms for academic and community engagements on inter-faith and societal issues, promotion of dialogue and capacity building for prevention, management and resolution of conflicts

Guiding Principles and Core Values

In ensuring that there is symbiotic correlation between theory and practice in its work, the CCMRE is guided by the following principles and values:-

- 1) Mutual acknowledgment of and respect for people's religious values;
- 2) Acceptance and understanding of different faith beliefs;
- 3) Upholding of various divergent and mutually reinforcing beliefs and using such to address common issues between people of faith;
- 4) Promoting the preservation of identity of different religious communities and its people; and
- 5) Enhancing common spaces for mutual learning of each other and common actions for societal prosperity

Objectives of CCMRE

- 1) To achieve a better understanding between Christians and Muslims and the associated socio-political environment;
- 2) To recognize and overcome stereotypes through academic approaches;
- 3) To make all parties, Christians and Muslims, in particular, and the wider society, in general, take part in learning processes;
- 4) To facilitate and promote mutual learning and appreciation between and among scholars, adult educators and students irrespective of historical, cultural and political diversities; and
- 5) Generate resources for research in the field of intercultural studies, including, but not limited to, publications, audio and visual materials

CCMRE Chair, Professor Esther Mombo and Coordinator, Dr. Joseph Wandera, receive Hon. Yusuf Hassan MP Kamukunji at St. Paul's University, Limuru.

(From Left) Emory University Prof. Jonathan Strom, Prof. Azumah, Prof. Joseph Galgalo –VC(SPU) Prof. Mojola, His Excellency David Angell, Hon. Hassan-MP Kamukunji, CCMRE Chair Professor Esther Mombo and conference participant, David Tarus (far right).

Honorable Yussuf Hassan, MP Kamukunji, plants a tree at St. Paul's University grounds prior to the Faiths and (in) Security Conference looking on the University Chaplain Rev. Githinji.

His Excellency David Angell, the Canadian High Commissioner to Kenya, plants a tree at St. Paul's University grounds prior to the Faiths and (in) Security Conference.

(From left) Canadian High Commissioner David Angell, the Vice Chancellor SPU-Professor Joseph Galgalo, MP Kamukunji Hon. Yussuf Hassan, SPU-Professor Mojola, Faculty of Theology.

Forward

For more than a decade, following the September 11, 2001 terror attacks in the United States, the world has witnessed the growing prominence of religious groups in local and trans-local conflicts that set them against states or members of rival ethno-religious traditions. In an increasingly secularized world, the return of religion to the centre of complex global political and security discourses is both interesting and worrying. From the clashes between rival religious groups in the Central Africa Republic to protracted skirmishes and kidnappings by *Boko Haram* in Northern Nigeria; from sieges and bombings by *Al-Shabaab* in East Africa to large scale civil wars by the Islamic State in Iraq and the Levant (ISIL); in numerous other examples across the world, the need to interrogate the place of religion in global conflicts as both cause and potential solution is more than urgent. In a world saturated by the media, people and ideas flow between the respective regions, providing religious groups with the capacity to reach out to co-religionists across national borders, thus posing danger to sovereign nation states. Across the world, a variety of groups in conflict zones offer convincing narratives, appealing ideological discourses and enticing promises both for the 'Here and Now' and in 'the Hereafter.' Many governments across the world have enacted legislation designed to curb acts of terrorism—jeopardizing peace and security--by religiously-motivated groups. The resultant use/abuse of powers by state apparatus targeting members of specific traditions under the rubric of fighting terror has also been cited in a number of countries as an infringement of human rights and freedoms. Additionally, there has been heightened tension within inter-faith relationships, especially in Africa, Asia and Europe.

In various parts of the world, but especially in the Middle East and to some extent in Africa, religious actors are raising their voices in support of a democratic order. Thus, all is not lost. Inter-faith alliances and intra-religious organizations have played increasingly critical roles in mediation and peace building processes at national and transnational levels. However, in a world characterized by religious fundamentalism, conservatism, militancy, terrorism and radicalization, religion has been viewed as a dangerous social phenomenon rather than as an ally in the enhancement of good governance and in the promotion of inter-ethnic/faith cohesion and the enlargement of cordial citizen-state relations.

This project was conceived in order to explore theoretical and conceptual frameworks that help to explain the place of religious traditions and (in)security in today's world. It was also intended to examine the causes and manifestations of religiously-motivated violence and to interrogate the responses of state and non-state agencies, pressure groups, donor countries and inter-faith forums. Issues of faith and security constitute multi-faceted phenomena, with implications for government policies, peace building, interfaith relations, human rights and for the war on terrorism. The conference was intended to problematize reports by the media, to frame issues of religion and security in Africa and to reflect on the impact of the 'war on terror' on the human rights of citizens within post-colonial African states. Additionally, the conference was intended to examine how theological education can contribute towards an understanding of the relationship between faith and security.

The conference featured three broad thematic areas:

- *Theological, theoretical and conceptual reflections on religion and violence*
- *The role of religious texts as motivation for and resolution of religiously-instigated violence and breaches of security*
- *The role of state and non-state actors in religiously-motivated violence within and across countries.*

The proceedings of the conference were intended to:

- *Build on the clear empirical and theoretical conceptualization of the intersection of religion and violence in Africa*
- *Enhance understanding of the role of religious textual interpretations as both cause of and solution to religiously-instigated violence in Africa*
- *Engage state security agencies, non-governmental organizations, academics from diverse disciplines, religious practitioners of various faiths in crucial inquiry concerning religion and violence in Africa*
- *Deliberate on mechanisms that various religious groups and other interested actors could deploy to address the phenomenon of religiously-based violence in Africa, through mutual inter/intra-faith collaboration*
- *Disseminate through appropriate means an edited volume containing well-researched case studies on religion and insecurity in Africa and smaller booklets with summarized reports of papers, round table deliberations and communiqués from inter-faith discussions*
- *Lay the foundation for subsequent conferences and workshops to be held at St. Paul's University or other African institutions, thus promoting further deliberations on similar thematic issues*
- *Plan toward closer collaboration between various actors in the security industry (state and non-state actors) and between the academy and faith practitioners, enhancing community mitigation of insecurity, thus influencing the development of key government policies toward the enhancement of inter-faith coexistence and dialogue.*

Participants

The conference brought together senior and junior academic scholars, religious specialists and practitioners, youth and women leaders, state actors, human rights advocates, security experts, the diplomatic and press corps and St. Paul's University community to reflect on the above themes. As a model of multi-disciplinary engagement and interaction, the forum aimed to balance academic discussions, grass-roots-based conversations and deliberations on the place of faith traditions in relation to emergent issues related to security and cordial co-existence.

Outcomes

Selected academic papers from the conference are to be published in an edited peer-reviewed volume. In addition, the conference findings are to be publicized in specially-edited reports for publicity through social media to the wider public. The conference constitutes the first step toward a wider process of engagement and exchange between the academy, religious practitioners and related state and non-state agencies on the question of faith and (in)security in Africa.

Papers, both theoretical and empirical, from disciplines such as theology, religious studies, political science, law, anthropology, social geography, sociology, media studies and related areas, were solicited.

Organizers

- Rev. Dr. Joseph Wandera (wandera@spu.ac.ke)
- Prof. Esther Mombo (emombo@spu.ac.ke)
- Dr. Halkano Wario (hwario@spu.ac.ke)

The conference was organized by the Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh by St. Paul's University and Egerton University in coordination with the support of Chandler School of Theology, Emory University; Danmission of Denmark; Egerton University; Duke Divinity School; Columbia Theological Seminary; EMW and Konrad Adenauer Stiftung.

Organizers Bios

Prof. Esther Mombo

[Esther Mombo](#) is the former Deputy Vice Chancellor (Academic Affairs) at St. Paul's University. Her PhD in church history is from the University of Edinburgh, UK. She is presently Director of International Partnerships and Alumni Relations and Chair CCMRE at St. Paul's University. Her research interests focus on church history, gender and theological education.

Dr. Joseph Wandera

[Joseph Wandera](#) is a Senior Lecturer in the Department of Religious Studies, St Paul's University and the Coordinator of the Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh. His PhD in Religious Studies (University of Cape Town) examined public preaching among Muslims and Pentecostals in Mumias, western Kenya, and its influence on interfaith relations. Dr. Wandera's research and teaching interests focus on the intersection between and within various religions and cultures and how these influence relations between members of various religious traditions.

Dr. Halkano Wario

[Halkano Wario](#) is a lecturer in Islamic Studies in the Department of Philosophy, History and Religion, Egerton University. He is an affiliate Volkswagen Foundation Humanities Research Fellow at St. Paul's University, Limuru, Kenya. He is engaged in a post-doctoral project on Muslim literature, cultures and epistemologies of religious knowledge in Kenya. He completed his doctoral studies at Bayreuth International Graduate School of African Studies (BIGSAS), University of Bayreuth, Germany, focusing on the localization of a translational Islamic movement in Kenya known as *Tablīghī Jamā'at*. His research interests include mediation and the mediaization of religious knowledge, religious transnational, religion and spatiality, religion and security, Islamic reformism in Eastern Africa and emerging trends in Islamic law in Africa.

Conference Record

A Concluding Comment

- In his introductory welcoming remarks, Prof. Joseph Galgalo (VC) rightly pointed out that dramatic and ominous changes on planet earth have been effected by the human presence. Human agency has been exercised for both good and ill. In the context of increasing inter-faith engagement, as creatures made in the image of God, we are challenged to choose and act for the sustainability and enrichment of life on this earth.
- The trove of information and reflection presented during these several days provides a remarkable basis for further research, reflection and action.
- The bold interrogation of core aspects of the holy texts of both Islam and Christianity presented during the conference commends a most careful consideration of text, context, and nuanced engagement.
- How to place, to engage, to compare and contrast the remarkable legacy and reality of African Religion within the current discourse on the relationship between the Abrahamic faith traditions remains an open-ended and on-going challenge.
- Participants to the conference were reminded that East Africa has for centuries served as an arena of intense engagement between African Religion in its multi-forms, and the imperial/missionary presence of both Islam and Christianity.
- Participants were challenged to consider negatives and positives in the embrace and exercise of religion. Both within and betwixt the religions of Islam and Christianity, understandings of the texts of holy writ vary considerably. As has been demonstrated repeatedly, narrow readings of one's own and the other's faith tradition/praxis can lead to tension, radicalization and even violence. Conversely, a respectful acknowledgment of the other's text and context has strengthened relationships within and amongst religious communities.

- The merits and utility of quantitative research methodology were well demonstrated. Reports on street level research and community engagement were equally impressive and appreciated. Special note was made repeatedly of the agency of women both at grassroots levels and in the academy.
- The academy generally and St. Paul's University in particular must be commended for the establishment, nurture and flowering of Muslim-Christian studies. The network of collaborative relationships, with tentacles into the far corners of this continent and beyond, is truly remarkable. Equally notable and appreciated are the community level initiatives and engagements amongst religious leaders, religious communities and individuals that have developed as a consequence.
- It was noted repeatedly throughout this conference that data generated by the academy and its students will lie inert unless it informs and motivates community level initiatives toward strengthening relationships, understandings and engagement between and amongst faith communities and beyond. Given the remarkable range of participants and actors present at this conference, the prospect of life-changing initiatives is promising.

Youth Pre-Summit

PRE-CONFERENCE YOUTH SUMMIT PROGRAM:

Venue: Jumuia Conference and Country Home: Date: 4th July 2016 Time: 0900 – 1300hours

TIME	TOPIC	SESSION
8:30 – 8:45am	Arrival & Registration	
8:45 – 9:00am	Introductions	
9:00 – 9:25am	The role of youth in peace building	
9:25 – 9:40 am	Group exercise	Break-out session
9:40 – 10:00am	Group presentations	Plenary
10:00 – 10:20 am	Tea Break	
10:20 – 10:45am	Identity, Nationhood and belonging and peace	
10:45 – 11:00am	Discussion	Plenary
11:00 – 11:25am	Faith & Insecurity :Drivers of Insecurity	
11:25 – 11:45am	Group exercises	Break-out session
11:45 – 12:00pm	Group presentations	Plenary
12:00 – 12:25pm	The relationship between youth and terrorism	
12:25 – 12:40pm	Group exercises	Break-out session
12:40 – 12:55pm	Group presentation	Plenary
12:55 – 1:10pm	Training closing remarks	
1:10 – 2:00pm	Lunch	

Youth-Summit Record

The Youth Pre-Summit Seminar took place on the eve of the larger Faith(s) and (in)Security Conference in Africa. The purpose of the summit was to empower the youth to participate effectively in the conference. The successful summit included more than 20 participants in a consideration of issues related to insecurity and peace building in Kenya. The Centre engaged two facilitators, John Mwangi and Judy Bisem, to explore topics related to peace, violence, security and insecurity in Kenya. Additionally, the summit interrogated the meaning of identity: how do people attain their identity; how does such identity relate to nationhood, to citizenship and to the role of youth in peace-building?

Youth Pre-Summit at Jumuia Country Home and Conference Centre, Limuru on July 4,2016

Youth Perceptions of Conflict

- A majority of the youth participants believed that conflict exists a priori between groups. A few believed that conflict also exists at the individual level. However, there was consensus among respondents that conflict exists between individuals as well as between people groups.
- The youth participants identified individuals--not groups--as the main actors in conflict triggered by personal property disputes, greediness, family disputes, illiteracy, ignorance, social or financial frustrations and unemployment.
- A significant number of youth suggested political parties as primary actors in local conflicts.
- According to both groups of respondents, the most significant reasons for conflict in all spheres are poverty, lack of education, intolerance, over-zealous loyalty to religion, fundamentalist religious leaders, political leaders, political conflicts, international actors and the absence of economic opportunities, especially for youth.

Perceptions of Security

The discussion began with an assessment of participants' awareness and perceptions of security and safety. Due to local sensitivities associated with the contexts of the respective youth groups, the focus of group discussion was structured to elicit views on security and safety. Participants were asked to share their understanding of what security means in their own communities. They were then asked a series of questions regarding their perspectives regarding the factors that contribute to security/insecurity in the respective communities and groups.

The discussion touched on the perceptions of participants regarding the role of local and international organizations in addressing security concerns, including questions regarding perceptions of the roles played by governmental, by nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), by law enforcement agencies such as the police and the military in maintaining security.

Youth at the Pre-Summit pause for a picture after their extensive training on July 4, 2017 at Jumuia Country Home and Conference Centre.

Nationhood and Identity

Nationhood was defined as a sense of 'belonging' among citizens and other inhabitants of any given territory--regardless of their prior identities--who identify with the symbols and institutions of the state.

Threats to nationhood include the following:

- Political elites of independent Kenya were seen to favor specific ethnic communities, creating commensurate public perceptions.
- Land became a major source of conflict.
- Ethnic identity was believed to be challenged by migration, especially when official land policies called for the movement of people groups. Devolved government has further enmeshed ethnic groups in boundary disputes.
- The exercise of nepotism in the allocation of jobs was identified among the factors that create conflict.

Open discussion following the facilitator's presentation identified a series of suggestions regarding the source of ethnic conflict in Kenya and the resolution of such conflict. Kenyans, it was agreed, should be proud of their ethnic identities. However, the exercise of fear and hostility towards each other should not be the way ethnic communities preserve themselves.

The foregoing discussion led to recognition of the need to forge a new sense of solidarity amongst Kenyans. Suggestions included the following:

- Religion should be deployed to bridge differences.
- Kenyans caught up in disputes over resources such as land, should look for peaceful ways of resolving the issues.
- The spirit of the constitution should be upheld.
- Intermarriages between warring communities should be encouraged.

Positive Community Actions

Community partnerships formed through sports, interfaith action and dialogue, multi-stakeholder *barazas* and community theatre should be fostered.

Youth and Peace Building

Youth comprise the largest portion of the Kenyan population and should be considered the key promoters of the peace agenda. Youth should educate themselves regarding the need for community leaders in rural areas. At the international level, youth can serve as peace ambassadors for their respective countries, promoting exchange programs in education, culture, science and technology, sports and tourism, linking young people in the pursuit and maintenance of peace. Nonviolent strategies for conflict resolution should be taught to the youth.

Role of Faith in the Quest for Security

Misperceptions of Islam as a violent religion were cited as was the existence of Christian militia in the Congo.

Suggestions for pro-faith engagement:

- Mobilize people in extensive peace networks
- Include religious moderates as well as conservatives
- Include single- faith as well as multi- faith actors
- Engage in advocacy, reconciliation and mediation
- Encourage people of faith to strive for peace and human rights

- Exercise moral and spiritual authority
- Initiate change&
- Mobilize moral ideas.

Following presentations by speakers and during plenary sessions, youth participants posed questions and made contributions especially regarding topics touching on the radicalization of youth, engagement with at-risk youth in countering terrorism, and the victimization of youth in high-risk communities by security agencies.

Youth observe the arrival of their MP Hon.Yusuf Hassan, just before he opened the conference.

OPENING REMARKS

BY REV. DR. JOSEPH WANDERA AT CCMRE CONFERENCE ON FAITHS AND (IN)SECURITY IN AFRICA, JULY 5, 2016, LIMURU, Kenya

Your Excellency the High Commissioner of Canada to Kenya, Kamukunji Member of Parliament Honorable Yusuf Hassan, Vice Chancellor, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Academics, distinguished guests, ladies and gentlemen:

On behalf of the Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh, I extend a warm welcome to you all and thank you for honoring our invitation to this conference. My name is Joseph Wandera and I work with St. Paul's University in the Faculty of Theology as coordinator of the Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh. Our theme for this conversation is "Faiths and (in) Security in Africa."

From the recent attacks on Turkey's foremost airport to occasional turmoil in Kenya's Eastleigh suburb, to Kenya's northeastern and coastal regions, the need to interrogate the place of religions in global conflicts as both cause and potential solution is more than urgent. It is urgent when a Muslim teacher dies because he shielded fellow bus passengers – Christians in this case - from a terrorist attack in the far-flung Kenyan town of Mandera. It is urgent when both Christians and Muslims protest real or perceived state terror against minorities, as was the case in the aftermath of the terrorist attack on the Westgate Mall in Nairobi.

Incidents of insecurity IN THE NAME OF Faith(s), plentiful enough in our time, are an enduring feature of religious life. Rituals of sacrifice and martyrdom and legendary tales of great battles abound within every religious tradition. In most cases the violent images are symbolic, but the reality of religion is clouded with actual events of violence and (in)security, inquisitions and internal attacks, sacrifices and martyrdoms, wars and conquests. Virtually every religious tradition has left a trail of blood. Some would argue that the

violent images in religion are greatly misunderstood. Religion itself is not violent, these defenders of religion would claim, but is, at its best, a voice of peace.

We agree, in part, for indeed most religious teachings are about peace. They preach tolerance and understanding of those who are different and advocate forgiveness and mercy in the face of opposition. The idea of killing is abhorrent to all religious traditions, and even the attempts to coerce and bully are regarded as anathema.

Yet as organizers of this conference we feel that there is value in having more conversations that focus on the seeming paradoxical relationship between faiths and insecurity. After all, these brutal passages in the respective religious texts exist, and despite the overwhelming peaceful claims of religious traditions, the fact remains that they are also filled with the symbols and language of violence. Why is this the case? It may well be, as some will claim, that these images help to alleviate real violence by symbolically displacing violent urges. It may also be true that religious violence is the rare exception rather than the rule.

Yet these are precisely the issues that need to be explained: how and why does religious language bespeak violent images and acts, and why, on what occasions, and how is it possible that symbolic violence can turn to real acts of bloodshed? The link between religion and violence extends to the early history of religious traditions. The sword of Islam and the cross of Christianity—execution devices—are only the most obvious indications of ancient associations with bloody images in religious culture. Amidst the predominant tales of pain and gloom, however, we must not forget the joyful warriors for peace and justice across Kenya, and beyond. Women like Rose Barmasai, in Kenya's volatile North Rift region, or Dekka Ibrahim, in the fluid northeastern region of Kenya, kept rural communities together, hoping for a shared future. Or consider the people of peace in other African communities, whose goodwill lubricates everyday life.

Ladies and Gentlemen:

It has been argued, generally, that the purposes of a university are three-fold: teaching, research and community service. In the context of St. Paul's University and the Center for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh, this conference on faith and (in)security in Africa creates an opportunity to probe the theoretical and conceptual frameworks that can help explain the place of religious traditions and (in)security on the continent today as a continuation of our commitment to combine teaching and research with community outreach. This is evident through the work of CCMRE in Eastleigh over the past 6 years, which has included collaboration with grassroots communities, the creation of space for conversation between members of different religious traditions, the facilitation of bridge-building among and within religious communities and the publication of our own research that maps Christian-Muslim relations in Eastleigh.

In this conference we have more than 20 young men and women drawn from across Kenya, who work with community-based projects as peace builders. They arrived a day before the opening of the conference to reflect on the theme so as to be part of this conversation.

Ladies and Gentlemen:

We trust that your presence here today will stimulate conversation for a shared journey and strengthen our ongoing engagement with various faith communities.

We thank Candler School of Theology, especially the Dean, Prof. Jonathan Strom, who in the month of January 2015 hosted me as a visiting exchange scholar and agreed to provide significant support for this conference. We thank Prof. John Azumah of Columbia Theological Seminary in the United States, who has also supported this event. I would like to thank other partners who have made this conference possible: Danmission (we acknowledge the presence of their Director Dr. Henrik), EMW, Konrad Adenauer Stiftung, Egerton University, and the Project for Christian-Muslim Relations in Africa. We thank the Canadian High Commission to Kenya whose Ambassador is present today, for supporting this event. Through your presence and the various earlier meetings with your First Secretary in charge of political affairs, Mr. Matthew Roy, Your Excellency, we trust a firm foundation has been laid for a strong partnership going forward. We thank Honorable Yusuf Hassan, the MP for Kamukunji, a great supporter of our work with communities in Kamukunji and especially in Eastleigh. Last but not least, we thank the administration of St. Paul's University, through the Office of the Vice Chancellor, for its support. Thanks to all scholars who will be sharing insights with us on this important topic.

“At a deeper level, the story of quest for peace is a story of each and every one of us--regardless of our faith persuasions, social status, backgrounds, scholarly interests or anything else. We must make our contributions and tell our stories--stories that show how similar our predicaments are. Our contributions may be very simple, humble and insignificant, but each story, each contribution counts, however small.”
Prof.Galgalo

It is my joy and a great honor to welcome you all to St. Paul’s University (SPU). We are privileged to host a gathering of strong representatives who are attending this conference from different parts of the world.

On behalf of SPU, I appreciate and recognize some key partners who have worked with us and supported us in the realization of this conference. We are grateful for the support of EMW, the Konrad Adenauer Stiftung, Danmission, PROCMURA, the Candler School of Theology of Emory University and the community representing various faith traditions from Kamukunji constituency in Nairobi. We appreciate the presence of Hon. Yusuf Hassan Abdi, the MP for Kamukunji, for his continued support and partnership with SPU through CCMRE. We are also privileged to have among us H.E. Ambassador David Angell. To you our dear guests and all participants, I say thank you all for coming. Welcome to St. Paul’s University.

SPU is an institution with a long history, having been on this site since 1903. We are a Christian ecumenical university offering programs in different fields of study, particularly since 2007 when we became a fully-fledged university following the award of a charter bestowed by the Commission for University Education on behalf of the Government of Kenya.

Because of our ecumenical identity we are well known for upholding such values as tolerance and commitment to an accommodative spirit that entertains every point of view and especially the voices from the margins of society. This is clearly evidenced in our flagship programs such as studies in HIV/AIDS and community-based care, programs such as development studies with keen interest in grassroots communities, designed creatively to provide students with valuable immersion experience in real life contexts. We are equally passionate about inter-faith relations and meaningful dialogue undertaken in contexts of mutual respect across various faith divides.

What motivates these kinds of initiatives? Why do we even care? We care because it is our noble duty as an academic community to contribute to the creation of better societies. We care because we are required to make our contributions and play our part to meet the basic human desire and quest for stable communities, for peaceful and harmonious co-existence, for good neighborliness in the interests of progressive, fulfilled and productively engaged communities.

At a deeper level, the quest for peace is a story of each and every one of us, regardless of our faith persuasions, social status, background, or scholarly interests. We humans find ourselves in a world--the only one we all share--in which our conflicts affect each and every one who belongs to this global community.

How can we tell our story so that it becomes the story of each and every one of us? Where do we begin to sketch a broad picture of the contextual realities of our times? It is not an exaggeration to say that we live in dangerous times. The world powers have accumulated for themselves nuclear and other arsenals capable of destroying the world ten times over. Alarm bells are ringing; the world is slowly but surely facing a potential catastrophe as a result of continued global warming. Apart from the damage affected by climate change, the world is experiencing devastating conflicts. The wars in Yemen, Iraq, Syria, Somalia, Nigeria and in several parts of Asia and South America are no longer isolated cases. Each of these conflicts has the potential to engulf the whole world.

The European struggle with the refugee crisis has been characterized by unprecedented mass migration of peoples from the Middle East and some African countries, bringing to mind the scale and effect of regional geo-political conflicts and what they mean for the world. The Oxford Research Group Report entitled, *Global Response to Global Threats*, identifies major areas of global threat such as climate change and militarization which 'unless urgent action is taken within the next five to ten years, it will be extremely difficult, if not possible, to avoid a highly unstable global system by the middle years of the 21st Century.'²

²<http://www.oxfordsearchgroup.org.uk/publications>

Such is the global context in which we find ourselves. Africa is more vulnerable than most parts of the world because of internal conflicts, governance and leadership crises, economic difficulties, not least because of international trade imbalances and trade deficits, mismanagement, unhealthy competition and negative exploitation of resources. Additionally, there are crises having to do with social progress; we contend with killer diseases such as malaria, TB and more recently, Ebola. In addition, Africa, perhaps more than ever, faces threats of religious, ethnic and political conflicts which marginalize abuse and discriminate against the goodwill of the masses.

It is time for every human being of goodwill to stand up to be counted. It is time that each and every one of us makes an effort to stop conflicts that abuse religious, ethnic, racial or social differences, conflicts that discriminate, subjugate, alienate and oppress others. We must make our contribution and tell our stories, stories that demonstrate how similar our predicaments are. Our contributions may be simple, humble and insignificant, but each story, each contribution counts, however small. We must reach out to each other as neighbors, as communities of faith, as scholars and through our shared stories build bridges across various divides. We must embrace and declare the brother/sisterhood of all humanity. We must realize what binds us together as one world, one common humanity; after all we finally desire the common good of peace and stability, progress and achievement, the good life and self-actualization. The world aspires to these values; the world cries for these values. Let us as people of faith show the way.

In a small way, this conference seeks to set participants on a 'shared journey' towards the vision of cooperation, partnership, good neighborliness and friendships to build and support communities of peace.

It is my honor to welcome you all to SPU and to wish you a fruitful time of engagement. Enjoy your stay; learn from one another, network and resolve to contribute to our common quest for building strong communities of peace.

Thank you very much and God bless you all.

'Strength in Diversity' David Angell.

Honorable Member of Parliament for Kamukunji, distinguished guests, ladies and gentlemen, all protocols observed,

Good morning all,

Before I begin, I would like to take this opportunity to thank Danmission, Emory University and the Programme for the Christian-Muslim Relations in Africa (PROCMURA) for co-hosting this event, as well as St. Paul's University, the Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh (CCMRE) and Dr Joseph Wandera for convening us here today to address the important topics of religion and security in Africa.

Indeed, every person should be able to live without concern for personal safety, and should be able to practice his/her religion of choice without fear or discrimination.

The promotion and protection of human rights, including freedom of religion or belief, peace and security, is an integral part of Canada's constructive leadership in the world.

Canada is well-placed to protect and promote peace and security around the world. Our own multi-cultural and multi-faith experience is reflective of our continued efforts to champion tolerance, pluralism and diversity in all spheres of society.

Indeed, Canada has made recognition of and respect for diversity a priority, both at home and abroad.

It is of the utmost importance that every individual is able to practice his/her faith within a peaceful and secure environment, protected from those who dispense a message of violence and intolerance.

Unfortunately, religious intolerance and discrimination continue to increase around the world, with extreme acts of violence often leading the daily news cycle.

Discrimination against religious and ethnic minorities, as with all forms of discrimination, causes unnecessary human suffering, spreads division, and contributes to a climate of fear, intolerance, and stigmatization. In extreme cases, we have seen it can lead to violent extremism.

Despite being an issue of serious debate as to the specific causes, and potential solutions, the world has not yet found an antidote to prevent individuals with extremist and intolerant agendas from promoting intolerance and violence.

These extremists have found successful methods to exploit marginalized populations.

That said, we must continue combating the issue through promoting tolerance and inclusion, and by continuing to develop our understanding of the root causes that lead people toward extremism.

Canada's Prime Minister Justin Trudeau has stated repeatedly that diversity is a source of strength, not weakness. Indeed, Canada is one of the most ethnically diverse countries on the planet, with over 20 percent of our population having been born outside of the country.

Originally a predominantly Christian nation, our country now comprises many people and religions. Our largest city, Toronto, has a large Muslim community – almost 8 percent of the city's population.

We believe we are strong because of our diversity - not in spite of it. Violent acts motivated by intolerance have no place in our country, and run contrary to the values of pluralism and acceptance.

East Africa, as well, has long been a center of religious diversity, tolerance and Muslim-Christian co-existence. Now more than ever it needs to capitalize on the strength of its diversity.

Canada will continue to work with like-minded partners to speak out against violence and discrimination and to promote peaceful coexistence and security, in Kenya, in Africa, and around the world.

Canada encourages you in this pursuit to better understand how we can foster peace and security and maintain communities that celebrate diversity and promote tolerance. We all benefit when that is the case.

To all here today in support of this event, Canada says thank you once again for your important work and dedication to this critical issue.

Asante sana!

Ministerial Address

'Speaking as a Muslim, murder is strictly forbidden in the Qur'an. Qur'an 6:151 says, '...and do not kill a soul that God has made sacrosanct...whosoever kills a soul, it shall be as if he had killed all mankind; and he who saves a life, it shall be as if he had given life to all mankind.' They do not represent me nor any other Muslim. Every religion rejects terrorism.' Hon. Yusuf Hassan

Your Excellency, the High Commissioner of Canada to Kenya, David Angell, the Vice-Chancellor of St. Paul's University, Professor Joseph Galgalo, the conference organisers, Dr. Esther Mombo, Dr. Joseph Wandera and Dr. Halkano Wario, distinguished scholars, ladies and gentlemen.

It is a great pleasure and honor to join you for the opening of this important conference on Faith and (in)Security in Africa. Those of us from Kamukunji have strong and beneficial links with the Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh (CCMCRE), which is an initiative of St. Paul's University.

We have just witnessed a bloody and most devastating week. The world has been assaulted by a series of irregular, hybrid and coordinated terrorist attacks in Istanbul, Mogadishu, Mandera, Dhaka, Baghdad and Madina. Extremist groups such as Al-Shabaab in East Africa, Boko Haram in West Africa, Al-Qaida and Isis in North Africa are - in the name of religion- wreaking havoc in large areas of the African continent. We are also witnessing the poisonous rise of fear and hate that breeds division and extremism in many parts of the world. Hardly a day passes without the news of another deadly attack on civilians, including children. Indeed, we live in uncertain and troubled times. Extreme violence is not an abstract reality for us. We have had real first-hand experience of violent extremism right here in Kenya and in our capital city, Nairobi.

My own constituency of Kamukunji has borne the brunt of violent extremism. My own neighborhood of Eastleigh has been struck by Al-Shabaab several times in the last five years, shedding the blood of the innocent. I have personal experience of this mindless violence. On December 7, 2012, we were coming out of a mosque - the house of God - when we were attacked with a bomb. I sustained serious injuries, but was fortunate to survive. Tragically eight people including two children lost their lives in this indiscriminate attack. Al-Shabaab has repeatedly struck Kenyan targets killing and maiming hundreds of civilians. Al-Shabaab is a Somalia-based militia group which claims to be fighting for the rights of Muslims.

These attacks that struck into the heart of our capital city, Nairobi, have shocked and terrified the public and have sparked growing fear and mistrust, poisoning relations between communities that have lived harmoniously side by side for many years. This is precisely the intention of those carrying out such attacks.

I am elected in what is probably the most cosmopolitan neighborhood in Nairobi. Kamukunji is a multi-cultural, multi-ethnic and multi-religious district. We are proud of our diversity. But when extremists strike, diverse communities like ours feel the most heat.

Immediately after the initial attacks, the public, the government and the media turned the spotlight on Kamukunji and especially on Eastleigh and Majengo. This took place shortly after I became an MP and encountered one of my biggest challenges as a legislator.

Everyone in these predominantly Muslim neighborhoods was seen as a prime suspect in the eyes of many Kenyans.

Some young people in these areas had become attracted to extremism. And if you look closely at the history of our young nation, you begin to understand why these communities are vulnerable to radicalization and violent extremism. Whether real or perceived, historic injustices, discrimination, exclusion, economic inequality and other structural injustices, have contributed to alienation and conflict.

Many of the young men lured to extremism come from backgrounds with broken families, rejection and identity crises. They acquire criminal records at an early age. They cannot obtain IDs easily or find employment. They therefore live in a legal limbo; they have no hope in the fairness of society and have developed a strong dislike for the establishment.

I know there is a school of thought that says poverty and underdevelopment are not the major reasons why a particular group or community gravitates towards violent extremism. I believe these young people join extremist groups, not because they believe in the ideology but because of feelings of hopelessness and despair. We have been able to mobilise the local, civic, youth, women, political and religious leaders and bring our community together. That is why we were able to restrain the rising tide of hatred, to lessen divisions and to stem intolerance within our community and to begin working together for the common good. Every day there are new obstacles and challenges, and at times unexpected developments that can

easily tip the balance toward chaos. The strong resilience of Kamukunji specifically and Kenyan society generally is remarkable.

Despite several attacks and provocations by Al-Shabaab, which is based on hatred and rejection of what we stand for, not a single Kenyan has rushed to attack his/her Muslim neighbor in anger or revenge. I am daily encouraged by acts of compassion and love from fellow Kenyan Christians.

And I am also encouraged by the goodwill of Muslims such as Salah Farah, a teacher from Mandera. On December 20, 2015, Salah was travelling from Mandera to Nairobi in a bus full of Christians returning home for the Christmas holidays when they were attacked by Al Shabaab terrorists. They tried to split up the Muslims and the Christians. But the Muslims refused. Muslim women gave their scarves to Christian women to cover their heads when they were ordered off the bus. Salah and others shielded the Christians and told the attackers to kill all of them or spare them all. The attackers were forced to abandon their attempt to kill the Christian passengers.

Among the survivors was Pastor Peter Waiguru and his son. Salah Farah paid the ultimate price. He died a month later from injuries sustained in the attack. That is what happens when humanity stands together. One of the biggest errors in countering violent extremism is to call the extremist militants "Islamic." As a result, Al Qaeda, Al-Shabab and Boko Haram carry the label of 'Islam' and are portrayed both in western political discourse and in the media as warriors of Islam. They wrap themselves in the identity of the Muslim community and proclaim their murders as actions undertaken in the name of Islam. By doing the same, we give them religious legitimacy that they do not deserve. Speaking as a Muslim, murder is strictly forbidden in the Qur'an. Qur'an 6:151 says, "and do not kill a soul that God has made sacrosanct... whosoever kills a soul, it shall be as if he had killed all mankind; and he who saves a life, it shall be as if he had given life to all mankind."

They don't represent me nor do they represent any other Muslim. I know no religion that condones terrorism. Every religion rejects terrorism. Terrorists are not strong believers who have turned violent, but rather violent extremists who manipulate religious concepts for their own purposes.

Finally, I would like to remember Jo Cox, the British MP, who was senselessly murdered outside her office in the UK. In her first speech to parliament, Jo said: "While we celebrate our diversity... we are far more united and have far more in common with each other than things that divide us." Beyond our differences, we must as people stand together to stop the poisonous rising tide of fear and hate that breeds division and extremism. We must reflect and follow Jo's example "to open our arms with love to our communities, our neighbours and to those less fortunate than ourselves, and to celebrate our tolerance and diversity."

I wish you a very successful conference as you deliberate and ask pertinent questions about extremists, giving special attention to their motivations, their organization, their recruitment and finance strategies and how we can most effectively prevent violent extremism and create peaceful and tolerant societies.

With those remarks I declare the Faith and (in)Security in Africa Academic Conference officially opened. Thank you.

[Dr. Godwin Murunga](#) presently the Executive Secretary of the Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa (CODESRIA) was a key speaker for the conference. His remarks were line with the topic of the conference by *Framing the Security Dilemma; conceptualizing peace and security*: He observed that State Security follows a Westphalia idea of Nation-State as sovereign. Sovereignty identifies the state as a key player in International Relations and confers on its rights and responsibilities within International Relations systems. Nation-states are defined by the national boundaries .Nation states also exercise absolute control over all forms of legitimate violence within its jurisdiction and confer citizenship rights and obligations which is the only recognition within an International System. In return, the State expects absolute loyalty; expressed in form of obedience to law, order and consummated via taxation.

It follows that the notion of security is state-centric: understood as largely external threatening boundaries but also internal when it threatens the very existence of the state; boundaries, institutions, people and values. Meaning that the notion focuses on the elitist (focus on protection for State actor located at the Centre of the State) limiting actors in the security sector to government actors. Thus, security provision is that people receive security so security is provided by the same State and its institutions.

Consequently, security is framed from a law and order logic designed to control people. Where it lacks capacity its ability to confer rights and offer protection is limited resulting in various forms of

vulnerabilities. Notably, for this notion to survive, the cause of insecurity must be clear, almost visible and obeys the rules of engagements and have ethical basis for violence.

Human security focuses on addressing vulnerabilities that affect people every day; touching on social welfare issues. However, it operated within and ultimately captured state security notions eventually being subsumed under state security frameworks.

Reframing the Security Dilemma: Religious implications

Dr Murunga feels that 9/11 was the turning point towards notion of security as stabilization. He refers to Samuel Huntington's *Clash of civilisation* and Bernard Lewis: *Roots of Muslim Rage*. How Lewis sees some unchanging essence in religious culture Islam; a dignity and courtesy towards others' which in moments of upheaval can give way to an explosive mixture of rage and hatred which impels even the government of an ancient and civilised ...to espouse kidnapping and assassination and try to find, in their Prophet, approval and indeed precedent for such actions.'pp22. Lewis drew a distinction between good versus bad Muslims.

Thus, there are no identifiable good Muslims to embrace and bad ones to terminate. Murunga notes that terrorism is not a religious war: bin Laden was a political actor not a religious leader. Terror groups mobilise religious doctrine for political purposes; what rationale they provide; it focuses on addressing grievances in society using religious vocabulary.

The nature of the threat is such that: Firstly, the security environment is murky and not defined along traditional notions of security thinking. The State is no longer the only actor and demands new thinking around security. Secondly, marginalization and communities at the edge of society paint a picture of the states inadequate capacity. Thirdly, asymmetrical warfare and information communication technologies dynamics have to be looked into.

In the case of Kenya beyond a State-centric notion, Murunga advises the reinforcement of state and human security. He further challenges police reform initiatives: intelligence heavy approach to policing driven by human rights, mobilizing citizens as co-producers of knowledge. That we should not elevate religious differences into security differences.

Dr Murunga concludes by noting the role of religious groups in redefining a new basis for security; He insists firstly, we go back to the basics; community-do unto others? Secondly, social welfare focus-providing the basics for those in the margin and thirdly, social justice against discrimination.

CCMRE Chair, Prof. Esther Mombo, calls on panelists to respond to Dr. Murunga's keynote address on the first day of the conference. (From left) Dr. Murunga (CODESRIA), Musa Ibrahim (BIGSASS), Dr Damaris Parsitau-Egerton University, Kizi-Ndzovu-Life and Peace Institute, Sheikh Irbard Ibrahim-Ghana, Jesse Maasai-Communications Director, Nyandarua County.

Kamukunji Youth, addresses the conference delegation following their summit.

Ambassador Kimani's Address

The Director National Counter-Terrorism Centre, Ambassador Martin Kimani speaks on State and Non-State Actors at the Conference on the last day.

Salim one of the Kamukunji Youth, engages the Director of the National Counter-Terrorism Centre, Ambassador Kimani, on security issues and government response.

Participants enjoy health break refreshments during the conference.

(From Left)Dr Johnson Mbillah-PROCMURA, Prof. Jonathan Strom –Emory University (Middle) and SPU Vice Chancellor Prof. Galgalo share during the health break at the Conference

CHIEF GUEST SPEAKERS

Vice Chancellor Joseph Galgalo

Prof. [Joseph D. Galgalo](#) is the Vice Chancellor and Associate Professor of theology at St. Paul's University. He has a PhD in Theology from Cambridge University and a BD from St. Paul's University. Prof. Galgalo has also served as an ordained minister in the Anglican Church of Kenya.

H.E. David Angell

High Commissioner of Canada to Kenya

David Angell (BA [Political Science], Yale University, 1986; MA [International Relations], University of Toronto, 1987; M. Phil [International Relations], University of Cambridge [Commonwealth Scholar]; joined External Affairs and International Trade Canada in 1989 and served abroad in Washington, D.C. (1991 to 1993); in Northern Ireland as adviser to Gen. John de Chastelain in the peace process (1995 to 1996); served at the Permanent Mission to the United Nations in New York (1996 to 2001), as Alternate Representative on the UN Security Council (1999 to 2000); and as High Commissioner in Nigeria and Ambassador to the Economic Community of West African States (2004 to 2007). In Ottawa, he served as Director General of the Africa Bureau (2007 to 2008); the International Organizations Bureau (2008 to 2009) and the integrated International Organizations, Human Rights and Democracy Bureau (2009 to 2012). He served as the G-8 Deputy Africa Personal Representative from 2001 to 2004 and, from 2007 to 2012, as the G-8 Africa Personal Representative and, as such, was closely involved in the organization of the 2002 and 2010 G-8 Summits in Canada, at Kananaskis and Muskoka. He is married to Kate, and they have two children, Alexandra and Jonathan.

Hon. Yusuf Hassan Abdi

[Yussuf Hassan](#) Abdi is a Somali-Kenyan politician, diplomat, social activist and former journalist. He is a former Director of IRIN. After working many years with the United Nations, he joined the Kenya parliament as a legislator in 2011. He represents Kamukunji Constituency in Nairobi County.

Ambassador Martin Kimani

[Martin Kimani](#), PhD, is the Director of Kenya's National Counter Terrorism Centre and Special Envoy CVE. Earlier he served as Permanent Representative and Head of Mission to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) in Nairobi.

In the past fifteen years, he worked in currency and bond trading, political risk analysis, academia, and multi-lateral diplomacy and counter terrorism. Ambassador Kimani holds an MA and PhD in War Studies from King's College of the University of London, and took a degree in philosophy from the University of New Hampshire in the United States.

He is a Fellow of the African Leadership Initiative and the Aspen Global Leadership Program. He was also the 2013 Distinguished African Visiting Fellow at the South African Institute of International Affairs.

Presentation: *State and non-State Actors and Violence-A case study of Kenya*

Dr. Godwin Murunga: *Key Note Speaker*

[Godwin Murunga](#) is the Director of the African Leadership Centre and also a Senior Research Fellow at the Institute for Development Studies at the University of Nairobi. He holds a BA (Honors) and MA from Kenyatta University and an MA and PhD in History from North-western University, Illinois, USA. Dr. Murunga is a former Executive Committee Member of the Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa (CODESRIA) based in Dakar, Senegal. He is widely published in various international journals including Africa Development, African and Asian Studies, Journal of Eastern African Studies, Journal of Higher Education in Africa and the AU Herald. He is currently co-editor of the Journal of Contemporary African Studies. Currently Murunga is the Executive Secretary of the Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa (CODESRIA). He assumed this position at a time when the academy is being asked to respond to the myriad challenges facing Africa.

Keynote Address: *Religion and Security in Africa: New Challenges in Conceptualizing Insecurity in Kenya*

Presenters' Profiles

Prof. Amy Adamczyk

[Amy Adamczyk](#) is Associate Professor of Sociology at John Jay College of Criminal Justice and the Programs of Doctoral Study in Sociology and Criminal Justice at The Graduate Center, City University of New York (CUNY). In 2005 she received her PhD in Sociology from the Pennsylvania State University. She holds MA degrees from the University of Chicago and the Graduate Center/Queens College, and she completed her BA degree at Hunter College.

Her research focused on how different contexts comprising nations, counties, friendship groups and personal religious beliefs shape people's deviant, criminal, and health-related attitudes and behaviours. Her research has been published in the *American Sociological Review*, *Social Forces*, *Justice Quarterly*, the *Journal of Health and Social Behaviour*, *Social Science Research*, *Social Science Quarterly*, *Sociological Quarterly*, *Sociology of Religion*, and the *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*.

With her colleagues she received the 2008 Donald MacNamara Award for the outstanding article of the year. In 2009 John Jay College awarded her the Donald MacNamara Award for Junior Faculty. In 2008, 2009, 2012, and 2016 she was the recipient of John Jay College's Research Excellence Award, and in 2011 she received the John Jay College's Midcareer Award. Her research has been supported with grants from the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation, the National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism, and the Chiang Ching-kuo Foundation.

Presentation: *Religion and Conflict in Africa: Examining the roles of survey research and social media for providing insight*

Nigeria is one of the few countries in the world that includes two major faith communities in roughly equal proportions (approximately 46% Muslim and 46% Christian). In recent years this religious division has been related in complex ways to political violence, hate crimes, and terrorism. For many years researchers have been using standard yearly or bi-yearly surveys, like the Afro-barometer or World Values Surveys, to better understand how religion shapes residents' attitudes and behaviors. Traditional survey methods have provided important insights into how religion influences perspectives of different groups, how religion views public policies and government activities, and the extent to which religion may either compel people to violence or encourage security and peace.

Although they have been useful, there are a number of limitations to traditional survey methods for understanding the public's views and how they relate to religious differences, violence, and security. For example, survey data are typically gathered only once or twice every two years, but key incidents and changes within the larger society can take place more frequently. Moreover, because respondents generally answer surveys in private, they may produce responses that are strongly shaped by people's attitudes about what they think the appropriate response to an issue is rather than what their true feelings are.

Indeed, the events of the so-called "Arab Spring" which resulted in the outbreak of mass protests across North Africa and the Middle East and the overthrow of several regimes caught many government officials, policy makers, and academics by surprise. In contrast to traditional survey methods, social media data, such as provided by Twitter, may be able to provide more insight into how religious discourse shapes public grievances and discussions of violence, as well as peace and compassion. The current study uses survey data from the Afro-barometer and World Values Surveys and Twitter data from residents living in Nigeria to better understand the relationship between religion, public grievances, and the motivation for violence and security. Among other things, the findings provide insight into how Muslims and Christians view each other, and the ways in which religion and religious discourse in Nigeria may either motivate people to violence or express compassion and love, thus helping to end physical aggression.

Dr. Abdulkadir Hashim

[Abdulkadir Hashim](#) is a Senior Lecturer in Sharia and Islamic studies at the University of Nairobi and an Advocate of the High Court of Kenya. He obtained his LL.B. in Sharia and Law in 1993 from Omdurman Islamic University, Sudan and LL.M in 1996 from the London School of Economics, University of London and completed his LL.D, University of the Western Cape, South Africa in 2010. He has published several articles and book chapters on Muslim Personal law and Kadhi courts along the East African coast. His research interests include administration of Muslim personal law in Kenya and Muslim intellectual history along the East African coast.

Presentation: *Taming Terrorism: State Policies and Muslim Grievances in Kenya*

Terrorism is a global concern and a threat to global peace and development. Terrorism is not a new phenomenon in Kenya; terrorist tendencies existed prior to independence in 1963. Most of the past terror activities were driven by socio-political and economic grievances. In contemporary Kenya, a paradigm shift of terrorism has been fueled by Islamic religious sentiments based on ideological and historical injustices that resulted in Muslim agitation beginning with the formation of the Islamic Party of Kenya in the early 1990s that continued with the founding of the Mombasa Republican Council and later, the Al-Shabab

threat. The menace was triggered by the attack of Kenya's Defense Forces on Al-Shabab territories in 2011. Since then, hundreds of innocent Kenyans have lost their lives in a warfare that has left Kenyans questioning the intent and validity of pursuing the terrorists in their territories. Among the striking features of terrorism in Kenya are the changing dynamics of radicalization and recruitment of Muslim youth from institutions of higher learning that include graduates from prestigious disciplines.

The terrorists responsible for the various attacks in Kenya range in age between 18 and 25 years. The age factor reveals the challenges facing youth who comprise a substantial part of the population in Kenya. The terror predicament has been related to security lapses caused by leadership failure to counter terror attacks, on one the hand, and by the laxity of Muslim leadership to mentor its youth, on the other hand. The Prevention of Terrorism Act of 2012 and the Security Amendments Act of 2014 were enacted to provide a legal framework for dealing with terror suspects. The media has blown terror atrocities out of proportion and associated Islam with terrorism, depicting a distorted image of Muslims waging war against Christians. Kenyan Christians managed to persevere throughout the challenging moments of deaths and casualties caused by terrorists, maintaining peaceful relationships with their fellow Muslim faithful. This research explored terror trends prompted by Muslim agitation and the undercurrents of terrorism and radicalization in Kenya. It is argued that the use of force against radicalized Muslim youth and indiscriminate mass arrests of Muslim suspects are counterproductive, providing breeding grounds for radicalization. Further, this paper suggests that there is a need for wider engagement to frame a counter narrative to deal with the causes of radicalization and the resultant terrorism. The 2010 Constitution of Kenya provides a solid framework with which to address most of the socio-economic challenges facing Muslims as well as marginalized citizens of Kenya. The study reveals much of the complex historical baggage inherited by Kenyans and in turn paves the way to solve many of the challenges facing the country, including terrorism.

Beatrice Nzovu-Ouma

[Beatrice Ndzovu](#) has 10 years of experience in the field of peace building. She is a facilitator of Conflict Transformation and Conflict Sensitive Approaches, Gender Mainstreaming and Gender frameworks with specific focus on Women, Peace and Security, as well as a trained and certified Peer Counselor. She has been involved in peace building at community, national and regional levels. She holds an MA in Peace Studies and Conflict Transformation from the European University Centre for Peace Studies (EPU) in Austria and a BA (Honours) in Sociology from Maseno University, Kenya. She is currently a programme advisor with the Life and Peace Institute focusing on Kenya.

Presentation: *Global (in)Security: A Farce of Faiths*

Religions are based on the premise of fundamental goodness. In both Christianity and Islam, peace is a key component. Yet, due to the emotive nature of religious beliefs and ideologies, degeneration in some instances to violence - ‘us’ vs. ‘them’--has been witnessed. Such religious (de)construction tends to dehumanize the “other,” creating psycho--religious distance, a recipe for violence. Situations become more dire when such distance is accompanied by strategic radicalisation expressed in violent extremism. The inability of religions to relate amicably with each other, to understand each other and to separate factual from non-factual ideologies, has meant that much of religious doctrine has been left to individual (mis)interpretation as well as tactical deception by actors interested in exploiting religion for a political and selfish agenda. Religious dichotomies in Kenya, linked to a political agenda of violent extremism in the absence of coordinated inter-religious dialogue, invoke state reaction. Such naïve reaction in the face of threats has compounded the problem of religious tension amplified by media reports, thus providing fertile ground for further radicalisation expressed as violent extremism and thus strengthening inter-religious gaps and stereotypes. The Kenya government tackles violent extremism in ways that exacerbate religious tensions. Religious actors--both Christian and Muslim--can play conciliatory roles that narrow the religious divides and cultivate the “fundamental goodness of religion and peace.”

Dr. Bernhard Koch

[Bernhard Koch](#) is the Deputy Director of the Hamburg-based Institute of Theology and Peace (IThF), sponsored by the Catholic Church in Germany. His research focuses on International Humanitarian Law, Military Medical Ethics, Pacifism, New Technologies and related philosophical discussions. The European Church Commission of Justice and Peace issued a memorandum on autonomous weapons systems co-authored by Bernhard Koch.

Presentation: *Revisionist Just War Theory and Christian Pacifism*

Dr. Damaris Parsitau

[Damaris Parsitau](#) is Director and Lecturer in the Institute of Women, Gender and Development Studies in Egerton University, Njoro, Kenya. Her areas of research and specialization include Religion, Gender and Politics, Gender, Gender Security, Civic Engagement, Public Life in Kenya, and Peace Building.

Presentation: *Engaging youth for a sustainable culture of peace and security in Kenya: The role of Faith-Based organizations*

The East African region, Kenya in particular, is experiencing a youth bulge, a predominance of young people in society that is likely to continue until 2050. This factor calls for urgent attention, given that the increasingly significant proportion of the population is growing at a high rate and is becoming increasingly restless and vulnerable in the face of the growing prominence of religiously inspired conflict such as the

ones perpetrated by Al-Shabab and other terror groups. Mobilizing the positive potential of youth lies at the heart of the challenge facing youth and peace. The youth can become an important human resource for development and a critical factor for social change, economic development and thus progress. They are central to the establishment of a culture of peace in Kenya. This research explored the roles of faith-based organizations and faith-inspired organizations in engaging youth in shunning violence, nurturing a culture of peace in the face of growing violence inspired by religious and cultural ideologies. The research sought to understand whether and how government interventionist strategies can co-opt religious actors with regard to the youth question in East Africa. It was based on ethnographic research carried out over the last five years and on religious peace building theory.

David Tarus

[David Tarus](#) is a PhD candidate in Christian Theology at McMaster Divinity College in Hamilton, Ontario, Canada. He is a graduate of Scott Theological College (B.Th.) and Wheaton College Graduate School (MA Theology). Previously he worked as the coordinator of Scott Theological College, Eldoret Campus, Kenya. He is a beneficiary of Billy Graham, Langham Partnership, and Scholar Leaders International scholarships. His published works include: “Social Transformation in the Circle of Concerned African Women Theologians,” and “The Significance of Intellectual Humility for Theologians Today” in the *Africa Journal of Evangelical Theology*; “John Stott and Biblical Preaching in Africa,” “Conquering Africa’s Second Devil: Ecclesiastical Role in Combating Ethnic Bigotry” in the *Online Journal of African Affairs*. He is co-editing a book titled, *A Christian Response to Terrorism: The Kenyan Experience*, to be published in 2016. His research includes Theological Anthropology, Political Theology, and Ecclesiology. His PhD dissertation examines the doctrine of the *Imago Dei* as a theological basis for ethnic cohesion.

Presentation: *Being Human in Kenya; Theological Anthropology in the Age of Terror*

This research explored Christian theological anthropology in response to the problem of terror in Kenya. Among key questions it sought to answer the following: What resources does the African traditional heritage offer in addressing the challenge of terrorist violence? What resources does Christianity offer in (re)shaping a new humanity capable of subverting violence? In what ways might the affirmation of the

sacredness of human life rooted in the doctrine of the divine image and on Christ help alleviate violence in Kenya? In addressing these concerns, the essay begins by underscoring indigenous African anthropology so as to establish a foundation for the study. It then articulates a contextualized theological anthropology centered on the doctrine of the image of God and on the doctrine of Christ as the basis for what it means to be human in contexts of violence. The thesis is that the Christian theology of the image of God and Christology in the context of the African *ubuntu* (community) provide resources for an anthropology capable of subverting violence. Thus this paper examined the place of Christianity, especially Christian theological anthropology, in the formation of people for peaceful co-existence in the context of terror and other forms of violence.

Prof. Gary LaFree

[Gary La Free](#) is a distinguished scholar and Professor of Criminology and Criminal Justice at the University of Maryland. He is a Fellow of the American Society of Criminology (ASC) and has served as President of the ASC and the ASC's Division on International Criminology. His research focused on the causes and consequences of violent crime and terrorism. His most recent book (with Laura Dugan and Erin Miller) is titled, *Putting Terrorism in Context*, published in 2015 by Routledge.

Presentation: *Religion and Conflict in Africa: Examining the roles of survey research and social media for providing insight*

Dr. Henrik Sonne Petersen

[Henrik Sonne Peterson](#) (PhD in Philosophy, BA in Philosophy and MTh) serves as Program Director of Danmission. Previously he served as lecturer in the University of Copenhagen, in the Teacher Seminary in Odense in Denmark. In Ethiopia he taught at the *Mekane Yesus* Seminary and at the Ethiopian Graduate School of Theology. He serves as Programme Manager for Church and Dialogue, Danmission.

Presentation: *Violence and Moral Attitude of Believers*

The relationship between religion and violence has taken on new dimensions since the attack on the Twin Towers in New York on September 11, 2001. At the core of these new actions lies what some have

referred to as a clash of civilizations, involving Muslims and Christians in special ways. In response, there has been a growing effort to understand religion, and how it relates to conflict management.

In this context, there is increased focus on the specific contribution of religious traditions to peaceful co-existence. Both secular and religious agents would benefit from a clearer understanding of the issues at stake. Although much attention has been given to religion and to religious leaders in the context of conflict management, it would be correct to say that the major portion of such attention has been concerned with situations in which religion has been used as a vehicle for the exercise of violence. It is important to understand the specific contribution of religious traditions in terms of praxis by lay believers as well as clergy, thus providing an 'intra-religious' perspective. An intra-religious perspective focuses on religious practice of worship, of religious life in prayer, of communal activity and the resultant formation of moral attitudes toward the religious other.

This paper focused on the following questions: What is it that, that forms and shapes relations between Christians and Muslims in East Africa and beyond? What are the specific contributions from Muslims and Christians to ongoing conflicts? Some research in conflict studies indicates that religions are involved in conflicts due to major issues such as ethnicity or competition for natural resources, while other research findings point to a complex range of issues such as neo-paternalism, urbanization and globalization as the basis for conflicts. A prominent contemporary example of the latter is provided by Professor Olivier Roy who in 2015 and 2016 suggested that terrorist attacks in Europe and the US can be understood as an Islamization of already radicalized persons, and not as a radicalization of Islam. However, in these examples the contribution of the religious actors, whether in the escalation or in the dissipation of the conflict, resembles that of other actors. It seems that the religious contribution to conflict is but one of multiple factors such as politico-social traditions, ethnicity, media, international business, and competition for natural resources. Since religious actors together constitute but one among many factors that contribute to conflict, it is illogical to accuse religious actors of causing all evils, vilifying religious traditions collectively. Religious actors should appreciate the contribution of others, understanding that only by working together can conflict be countered, and the common peace be built.

Irbard Ibrahim

Irbard Ibrahim is an authoritative voice in Ghana advocating Inter-Religious Peaceful Co-existence with a wide appeal in Africa and beyond. He is an alumnus of the US Government's International Visitor Leadership Programme on Conflict Resolution, Washington D.C. He is currently a Peace Ambassador for Ghana's general election held in November 2016. He presents regular peace lectures in universities, faith-

based organizations, and traditional chieftaincy institutions. He conducts daily TV and radio interviews on counterterrorism and international security on Voice of America, BBC, Thompson Reuters, among other media in Ghana and West Africa. As an Imam and fluent Arabic speaker, he advises Ghana's Government and state security agencies on transnational militant organizations such as *Boko Haram*, *AQIM*, *Ansar Dine*, *Al Qaeda*, and *ISIS*. He promotes peaceful religious co-existence and decries recruitment for violent extremist activities.

Presentation: *The Role of African Governments, Civil Society and the Clergy in the fight against Terrorism in the Continent*

In his presentation, he offered a critical assessment of the role of governments in countries such as Nigeria, Somalia, Kenya, Algeria, Egypt and Tunisia, tackling the scourge of terrorism and advising governments to partner with civil society and the clergy toward the formation of peaceful societies.

Prof. John Azumah

[John Azumah](#) is a Professor of World Christianity and Islam and serves as the Director of International Programs, Columbia Seminary in the USA. Dr. Azumah specializes in Islam and Christian-Muslim Relations and is interested in Islamics, Christian Theology of Religions, Missions and Missiology. His current research area is in World Christianity and Islam in the global south. He holds a PhD from the University of Birmingham, UK and an MA from the University of Birmingham, UK.

Presentation: *The Role of Holy Writ in religiously inspired Violence in Africa*

To the African, religion is necessary to life like water is necessary to fish, a truism requiring no elaboration or defence. Since time immemorial, Africans have been deeply religious, long before the advent of the two monotheistic and missionary religions of Christianity and Islam. Africa has served both as a haven of religious tolerance and as a theatre for religiously inspired conflicts. Among the key additions bequeathed by Christianity and Islam to the African religious cosmology has been the introduction of holy writ or scriptures. This chapter explores how the Bible and the Qur'an have been deployed to instigate conflict as well as to foster reconciliation and peaceful co-existence in Africa.

Prof. John Chesworth

[John Chesworth](#) is a Research Officer for Christian-Muslim Relations and led the Bibliographical History 1500-1900 Project, based at the School of Philosophy, Theology and Religion at the University of Birmingham. Among his most recent publications: *Using the "other": Morisco "borrowings" from Christian authors*, in Borja Franco, et al. (eds), *Identidades Cuestionadas: Coexistencia y*

conflictos interreligiosos en el Mediterraneo (ss. 14-18), Valencia: University of Valencia, 2016, 225-3; 'Muslim and Christian perspectives on animal slaughter: Reflections on East Africa', in J. Mbillah and J. Chesworth (eds), *From the Cross to the Crescent vol. I no. 2* (Nairobi: PROCMURA, 2015) 89-96; *The Character of Christian-Muslim Encounter: Essays in Honour of David Thomas*, D. Pratt, J. Hoover, J. Davies and J. Chesworth (eds) (Leiden: Brill, 2015); and *Christian-Muslim Relations. A Bibliographical History 1500-1900*, volume 6 onwards D. Thomas and J. Chesworth (eds) (Leiden: Brill, 2014 onwards).

Presentation: *Faiths and (in)Security from a historical perspective*

The sixteenth century was a period of new encounters in Eastern Africa. It marked the Christian Portuguese encounter with Islam, whilst in Ethiopia a Muslim group rose up against an established Christian kingdom. Those engagements led to shifts in loyalties whilst old perceptions and misperceptions were applied to the 'other.' This paper presented a series of 16th Century encounters in Eastern Africa, exploring both Christian and Muslim sources, and considers which lessons apply to our current century and situation.

Dr. Johnson Mbillah

[Johnson Mbillah](#) is the General Advisor, Programme for Christian Muslim Relations in Africa (Procmura)

Presentation: *Faiths and insecurity in Africa: A provocative but realistic analysis of the situation*

Mr. John Mwangi

[John Mwangi](#) is Lecturer in Peace and Conflict Studies at the Faculty of Social Sciences, St. Paul's University, Kenya. He is currently a PhD candidate in International Relations at the United States International University (USIU) Nairobi, Kenya. He holds an MA in International Relations and a BA in Communication. Selected publications include a 2014 co-authored article in the Journal of Third World Studies on 'Business Travails in the Diaspora: The Challenges and Resilience of Somali Refugee Business Community in Nairobi, Kenya. His most recent publication is a 2015 book chapter on 'An Assessment of Kenya's Counterterrorism Responses in the Horn of Africa Post 9/11,' published by the University for Peace Africa Program, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. His research interests revolve around Peace and Security studies, Refugee studies, and Media portrayals of terrorism with a specific focus on the Horn of Africa. John is a 2016/17 Social Science Research Council's (SSRC) Next Generation Social Sciences in Africa Fellow.

Presentation: a) *Narratives of Radicalisation and Violent Extremism: Voices from Nairobi Residents*

Mwangi has cited terrorism as a global challenge that is reconfiguring the nature of security in Kenya. Radical terrorism has become more pronounced following Kenya's 2011 military engagement in Somalia.

By means of fieldwork, this study interrogates the pathways to youth radicalization and attendant violent extremism. The study listens to ‘narratives’ and ‘perspectives’ in order to ascertain what constitutes the trajectory of youth and women from Nairobi’s Eastleigh and Majengo areas. The context of this radicalization is linked to the rise and influence of Islamic fundamentalism. Youth radicalization targets practicing young Muslims and recent converts to the Islamic faith. This study ‘listens’ to the subjectivities of human life and the associated perceptions of selected residents in Nairobi with regard to youth radicalization that is now linked to terror attacks. It also ‘listens’ to community discourse regarding suggested interventions that address threats posed by radicalization and violent extremism in Nairobi. It used a qualitative observation approach, group and individual interviews complemented by various primary and secondary documents. It was a research effort designed to enlarge the academic literature on radicalization and violent extremism from a community perspective. Previous counter-terrorism studies have focused on state explanations of the security threat. The findings of the study are useful for government policy formulation and for civil society planning.

b) Media Framing of the War on terrorism and its implications for human rights; the case of Garissa Terrorist Attacks

Dr. John Ndavula

[John Ndavula](#) teaches in the Department of Communication Studies at St. Paul’s University. He graduated with a PhD in Mass Communication from Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya. His research interests centre on media effects.

Presentation: *Media framing of the war on terrorism and its implications for human rights; the case of Garissa terrorist attacks*

John Ndavula and John Mwangi explored how mainstream media framing of the war on terror is re-shaping the human rights discourse in Kenya. Their study explores how Kenya’s counter-terrorism responses since the late 1990s have impacted the realization of human rights. The study examines the media portrayal of select human rights derogations such as refoulement of refugees and asylum seekers,

securitization and profiling of Muslim identities, and torture. The rights derogations are assessed within existing human rights provisions enshrined in both domestic and international law. The study adopts a qualitative inquiry and reflects insights and narratives from field research. The findings indicate increased media tolerance with regard to the rights of civilians in the context of the war on terror. The study encourages media not to abandon its human rights advocacy in the context of the war on terror.

Julius Kithinji

[Julius Kithinji](#) is a lecturer at St. Paul's University, Department of Theology, with research interests in the New Testament.

Presentation: *Bible in the Age of Religious Radicalisation: An Enigma or Assistive Literature*

Religious radicalism, closely allied to contemporary terrorism, is a serious phenomenon that plagues our age. Terrorism is currently the world's major threat to peace. Terrorism is linked more to religious radicalism than it is to economic and political factors or any other ideology. However, the solutions being offered to downgrade terrorism in the world scene are mainly military in nature rather than religious. In Kenya, many counter terrorism measures have been suggested and implemented including surveillance, 'hotlines,' security checks, and anti-terrorism trials. However, major methods for curbing or mitigating the effects of terrorism have not seriously considered religious texts as sources for the mitigation or elimination of terrorism. In fact, many of the anti-terrorism seminars on offer in institutions of learning in Kenya hardly resort to any religious texts (whether the Quran or the Bible) as dialogue support in the war against terrorism. In light of that lacuna, this paper evaluates the utility of the Bible in countering the ideology of religious radicalism. It deploys a post-colonial biblical hermeneutics as its theoretical orientation to interrogate the gospel of Mark, paying particular attention to the theme of discipleship. In doing so, it reviews the Jesus movement and how it was organized as a clandestine movement similar to terrorist groups.

Prof.MachariaMunene

[Macharia Munene](#) is Professor of History and International Relations at the United States International University (USIU), Nairobi, Kenya. He holds a BA (History), Gonzaga University; MA (History), PhD (Diplomatic History), Ohio University, Athens. Specialty areas: diplomatic history, Africa in world history and politics, conflict analysis, Kenyan history, politics and foreign relations. He also serves as a Visiting Professor at *Universitat Jaume-I, Castellon*, Spain, and as a Professorial Friend of the National Defense College, Karen, Nairobi, Kenya.

Presentation: *The Abuse of Faith and States*

Macharia posits that three concepts need attention in a discussion on “Abuse of Faith and States.” These are: *state*, *faith*, and *abuse*. When the three elements are juxtaposed, they present a disturbing reality that plagues humanity and creates a sense of insecurity everywhere. Ideally, *abuse* should disappear but this is unlikely, given the competing interests that exist in the context of particular geopolitical realities. *Faith* is central to the development of a people’s identity and is therefore a core interest that needs to be protected. In the process of protecting *faith*, there is the possibility of reducing it to a tool of abuse to advance parochial interests. When applied to other people, it can become an instrument of imperialism. Such an abuse of *faith* can arouse reactions that lead to violence and war.

Musa Ibrahim

Musa Ibrahim is a young scholar from Nigeria. He obtained a BA from Ahmadu Bello University, Nigeria, and an MA from the University of Cape Town, South Africa. At UCT he worked in a collaborative project on *Media, Religion and the Public Sphere in Contemporary West Africa*, directed by Prof. Abdulkader Tayob. His MA thesis investigated Islamic radio and television programming in Ghana. Musa Ibrahim joined the Bayreuth International Graduate School of African Studies (BIGSAS), University of Bayreuth (Germany) as a junior fellow/PhD student in 2014. His project investigates Islam and film in northern Nigeria. His research focuses on the activities of Northern Nigerian Filmmakers (Kannywood) and Sharia enforcement agencies (Hisba and Censorship Boards) within the public sphere, on the one hand, and the new Sharia regime, on the other. He is working under the supervisory team of Dr. Franz Kogelmann and Prof. Rüdiger Seesemann of the University of Bayreuth, and Prof. Brian Larkin of Barnard College, New York, USA. His general research interest is interdisciplinary and covers contemporary Islam, the media, and the public sphere.

Presentation: *Internal Islamic Pluralism, Sacred Text, and (in)Security: Analyses of Ulamā and Local Filmmakers' Crisis in the Sharia Context of Kano, Nigeria*

Musa noted that for the past one and half decades (1999-2015), and since the re-introduction and re-implementation of Sharia law in northern Nigeria, there have been many conflicts that have been connected either directly or indirectly to the resurgence of religion within the regional socio-political and economic space. Multi-faceted religious conflicts, human right concerns, together with the *Boko Haram* insurgency and its related trends have become topical issues within the context of Islamic resurgence in northern Nigeria. While academics have been grappling with multiple theories, trying to explain these phenomena (within the context of the re-introduction of Sharia), it is clear that some minority groups both to the right or left of the Sharia implementation express disenchantment either in the form of marginalization or annihilation. In other words, some groups at the periphery express their discontent by excluding the dominant group through (*mis*)interpretation of the text, thereby acting only for their own interests. Thus is religion perceived and appropriated differently by different people based on interest and opportunities, usually followed by violent conflict between followers of such ideologies. The research

considered how multiple interests are established and expressed through (mis)interpretations of the text and how that generates tensions capable of exploding into violent conflicts. Indigenous Muslim filmmakers in the northern Nigerian film industry believed that some textual interpretations by the mainstream *ulamaat* were designed to annihilate them. They therefore resorted to their own interpretations of religious texts to justify their interests within the prevailing religious context.

Ms Odette Murara

Odette Murara is a PhD student (Anthropology) in the department of Anthropology and Sociology at the University of the Western Cape (UWC). She holds a BA degree in business studies from the Africa University, Zimbabwe and an MA in Development Studies (UWC) with an MA thesis on xenophobic experiences of foreign African students at UWC. Her current research interests focus on the performance and the politics of diversity, and on the ways in which individuals and groups negotiate for peace in contexts of exile. Focusing on migrants from the Great Lakes Region within local South African communities, she explores the ways in which migrants negotiate their everyday diversities among themselves and with South Africans. MsMurara has participated in various research efforts on African migration and diversity. She has worked as a researcher for the South African Medical Research Council (MRC) in Cape Town in the 'Women's Health and Migration Study' project 2012; and within the Sociolinguistics of the Super Diversity Project in Cape Town. She is a recipient of a fellowship from the Next Generation -Social Science Research Council (SSRC) of America, for PhD dissertation completion. She is a member of the American Political Science Association (APSA), and a member of the International Political Science Association (IPSA).

Presentation: *'The devil' is the enemy and not 'the foreigner': The Church as a resource for peace and security in the South African migrant community*

While the dominant discourse in contemporary South Africa is on the contentious persistence of xenophobia, insecurity and exclusions that are experienced within the migrant communities, this paper focuses on an issue that has been neglected in both social and political considerations, namely, the everyday interactions among migrants and local South Africans. The latter touches on the ways in which African migrants and locals have mediated their encounters within South Africa's fragmented migrant community. What are the situations that make their conviviality possible in an environment in which conflicts are also possible? The study found that despite the tension within which migrants and South Africans have lived, in their local settings there are resources that they use to negotiate their differences. Clearly religion is one such resource. Through the medium of church both migrants and locals have managed to find each other as

brothers and sisters, a reality that broadly bespeaks the contemporary understanding of peace and security in post-colonial Africa. With a focus on migrants from war-torn countries of the Great Lakes Region, the study situates itself within the broad theoretical perspective of cosmopolitanism from below. The paper draws largely on the ethnographic evidence from the local Pentecostal Church and from a set of interviews with both migrants and locals in the informal settlement of Phoenix in Cape Town.

Dr. Paul Mwangi

Dr. Paul N. Mwangi, BA, MA, PhD. (Nairobi University), PG-Cert Belfast, MATE London School of Theology and Middlesex University UK, lecturer in the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, South Eastern Kenya University. His research interest is interdisciplinary on development, political, religious, ethical, anthropological, sociological and gender approaches to contemporary challenges. He studied and qualified for PhD, MA and BA (Hons) at the University of Nairobi. He also has a Post Graduate Certificate in Theological Education from Belfast Bible College, Northern Island, and an MA in Theological Education from the London School of Theology in conjunction with Middlesex University UK. Dr. Mwangi has served as Chairman of the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, School of Humanities where he also lectures on various subjects related to religion, social change and development. He is currently the Dean of Students at South Eastern Kenya University. He has authored two chapters in two different books: *The Role of Missionary Religions in Global Ethics* (2012) and *Celebrating Human Diversity in Building the Kingdom of God on Earth: A Bahai Perspective* (2009). He is the co-editor of, *A Century of God's Household in the Diocese of Mount Kenya South* (2002).

Presentation: *The Role of language and Communication in Religious Fundamentalism*

Mwangi notes that in the 21st Century, religious fundamentalism is raising eyebrows as it exercises organized violence against those of different religious practice and expression. The geographic spread of religion-related violence (Al Shabaab in Somalia, Kenya and Uganda, The Lord's Resistance Army (LRA) in Uganda and Sudan, Boko Haram in Nigeria, Islamic State (IS) in Europe and Asia), may lead, if not checked, to national, regional and even global instability. Christian fundamentalism and Islamic fundamentalism are on the increase in regions where the two religions share an almost equal number of followers. This research analyzed the link between religious language and communication, on one hand, and religious fundamentalism, on the other, noting how the two have contributed to insecurity in Africa and beyond. Religious language and communication in the current research are taken as important variables in a consideration of religious fundamentalism within Christianity. The central thesis of the paper is that in most cases religious fundamentalism is founded on weak and unsound teachings that deviate from the orthodox teachings of the respective religion.

Dr. Twase-Munga WaChidongo

Tsawe-Munga is a lecturer at Pwani University. He has a PhD in Theology from University of Birmingham UK, an MA in Religions, Politics and International Relations from The University of Wales Lampeter, a BA in theology from Kenya Methodist University and a Diploma in Theology from St. Paul's University. His area of specialization, research and supervision is focused on inter-faith relations with an emphasis on inter-religious dialogue among world religions and African indigenous religion. He has an interest in peace, development and governance studies, based on inter-religious interrogation of the crucial elements in global insecurity.

Presentation: *Religious Encounter in African Schools: Can it be a platform for addressing insecurity?*

Religion in Africa constitutes a significant dynamic in daily affairs. Christianity, Islam and African Indigenous Religion have all been practiced consistently since time immemorial with Hinduism, Sikhism and Buddhism dominating urban regions where Asian communities are present (Mbiti 1975). In contemporary Africa the growth of diverse multi-cultural and multi-religious societies has affected the movements of communities on a global scale. These circumstances have positively enriched societies by, for example, enabling children and students from different religious and cultural backgrounds to attend the same schools, colleges, universities and places of social recreation. On the surface, it is indeed the case that differences of culture and religion may not be so noticeable, due to the fact that people engage in routine activities without considering their religious differences. What has sparked tensions in some African states is the specter of global radicalization of religion. In his study, Tsawe explores the religious encounter in African schools as a basis for reforming religious education toward a pluralist religious society that averts insecurity. To this end, Kenya served as a case study. The author engages particular religio-educational streams of thought that accommodate the interests of a pluralist and multi-religious society. The author critiques the current exclusionary mode of religious education by noting its side-effects, and therefore suggests a paradigm shift in religious education in Kenya, and in Africa generally, to an inclusive all-religions education model in order to reform society by meeting and addressing the contentious issues of a pluralist society.

Ukoha Ngwobia

Ukoha Ngwobia is currently an MA Candidate in Islam, Christian-Muslim Relations at St. Paul's University, Limuru, Kenya. He is the Director of Lay Development and Leadership Training in the Presbyterian Church of Nigeria. He is a lecturer at EssienUkpabio Presbyterian Theological College, Itu-Akwabom State and nominee for Area Advisor for the Programme for Christian-Muslim Relations (PROCMURA) in Eastern Nigeria.

Presentation: *Hermeneutical Basis for Religious Insecurity in Christian-Muslim Relations in the South Eastern Nigeria*

Prof. Womack Deanna Ferree

[Deanna Womack](#) is Assistant Professor in the History of Religions and Multi-faith Relations at Emory University's Candler School of Theology and the Director of Candler's Leadership and Multi-faith Program (LAMP). She teaches on the subjects of Islam in America, Christian-Muslim Relations, and Global Religions. Womack came to Candler from Princeton Theological Seminary, where she earned her MDiv, ThM and PhD. Her research combines commitments to inter-religious understanding, Christian-Muslim dialogue, and American-Arab relations. Ordained in the Presbyterian Church (USA), Womack spent two years in Lebanon working as a Christian educator. She has lectured and published widely and is

the recipient of numerous awards for her scholarship, including honors from the American Academy of Religion.

Her presentation on *'Discourses of Insecurity: American Political and Religious Perceptions of Global Islam'* addresses how Islam which has been at the forefront of American public discourses since September 11, 2001 and the more recent emergence of the Islamic State (or ISIS) in Syria and Iraq and attacks by ISIS-affiliates around the globe have coincided with a new wave of fearful rhetoric aimed at Muslims in America and abroad. The political rhetoric in social and broadcast media, polarizing anti- and pro-Muslim marches have marked urban landscapes especially in the recent months. The chapter hence examines the impacts of American discourses about Islam – voiced by politicians, Christian leaders, and the news media – in response to acts of terrorism by those who self-identify as Muslim. The author considers the social impacts (such as the way Islamophobia disrupts the daily lives of Muslim Americans) and the political impacts, like proposed immigration laws and changes in US foreign policy that stem from the American culture of insecurity about Islam. While the starting point for the research on which the chapter is based is the American – rather than the African – context, the author aimed in the end to discern the implications of such American discourses for African Christians and Muslims. This is an important area of inquiry since the number of African-born immigrants in the US has climbed steadily since the early 2000s, with Nigerians as the largest group and significant numbers from East Africa, including Ethiopia, Kenya, and Somalia.

From left :The Chair CCMRE Prof. Mombo and the coordinator Dr Wandera speak engage a bigger audience on 'The Last Word' ,KTN over the State of Africa's Interfaith Relations ahead of the Faiths and (in) security conference.

Prof. Azumah and Prof. Jonathan Strom in conversation during tea break at the Faiths and (in)Security Conference.

Life and Peace Institute's Kizi Ndzovu (holding the mic), responding to a discussant during the conference. (From left) Musa Ibrahim, Damaris Parisatau-Egerton and Irbard Ibrahim-Ghana.

St.Paul's John Mwangi(middle) responding to a question on his papers alongside (from left) Dr. Parsitau-Egerton University,(right) St. Paul's Dr. Ndavula.

Conference Program

FAITHS and (IN)SECURITY IN AFRICA CONFERENCE

July 4-8, 2016

Organisers: Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh (CCMRE) - St. Paul's University

Venue: *Jumuiya* Conference & Country home, Next to St. Paul's University, Limuru, Kenya

Monday, July 4, 2016	
9.00-1.00	Youth Pre- Summit
Arrivals and Reception	
Tuesday, July 5, 2016	
7.00-8.45	Breakfast
9.00-9.50	VC's Welcome: Prof. Joseph Galgalo: St. Paul's University
	Official Opening
	His Excellency David Angell: Canadian High Commissioner to Kenya
	Hon. Yussuf Hassan, MP Kamukunji
Theme	
Theological, Theoretical and Conceptual reflections on Religion and Violence	
9.50-10.20	Dr. Godwin Murunga: Religion and Security in Africa: New Challenges in Conceptualizing Insecurity in Kenya
10:20- 10:50	Plenary
10.50-11.20	Health Break
11.20-11.45	Dr. John Chesworth: Faiths and (In)Security from a Historical perspective
11.45-12.10	Dr. Johnson Mbillah: Faiths and Insecurity in Africa: A Provocative but realistic analysis of the situation
12.05-12.30	Mr. Musa Ibrahim: Internal Islamic Pluralism, Sacred Text, and (In)security: Analyses of <i>Ulamā</i> and Local

Filmmakers' Crisis in the Sharia Context of Kano, Nigeria	
12.30-12.55	Dr. Henrik Sonne Petersen and Dr. Joseph Wandera: Violence and Moral Attitude of Believers
12.55-2.00	Lunch Break
2.00-2.25	Dr. Bernhard Koch : Revisionist Just War Theory and Christian Pacifism
2.25-2.50	Prof. Macharia Munene: The Abuse of Faith and States
2.50-3.15	Rev. David Tarus: Being Human in Kenya: Theological Anthropology in the Age of Terror
03.15-3.40	Dr. Uta Andree: Faith and Security as an Issue of a Theology of Migration
3.40-4.20	Practitioners Round Table Dr. Duncan Omanga, Mr. Al Amin Kimathi, Mr. Jesse Maasai, Mama Lulu Isaac, Dr. Rashid Abdi, Dr. Godwin Murunga
Wednesday, July 6 2016 Theme Religious Texts and Violence	
7.00-8.45 Breakfast	

9.00-9.30	Prof. John Azumah: The Role of Holy Writ in Religiously Inspired Violence in Africa
9.30-9.45	Response: Dr. Rashid Abdi:
9.45-10.00	Plenary
10.00-10.30	Break
10.30-11.25	Dr. Julius Kithinji: Bible in the Age of Religious Radicalism: An Enigma or Assistive Literature
11.25-11.50	Mr. John Mwangi: Narratives of Radicalization and Violence Extremism: Voices from Nairobi residents
11.50-12.15	Dr. Paul Mwangi and Dr. Lydia W. Wangungu: The Role of Language and Communication in Religious Fundamentalism.
12.15-1.00	Practitioners Round Table Rev. Ukoha Ngwobia, Dr. Julius Kithinji, Prof. John Azumah
1.00-2.00	Lunch Break
2.00-2.25	Rev. Ukoha Ngwobia: Hermeneutical Basis for Religious Insecurity in Christian-Muslim Relations in the South Eastern Nigeria
2.25-2.50	Mrs. Beatrice Nzovu-Ouma: Global (In)security: A farce of faiths
2.50 - 3.15	Ms Odette Murara: 'The devil' is the enemy and not 'the foreigner': The church as a resource for peace and security in a South African migrant community.
3.15-3.40	Prof. Amy Adamczyk and Gary LaFree: Religion and Conflict in Africa: Examining the roles of Survey Research and Social Media
Thursday, July 7, 2016	
Theme State and Non-State Actors and Violence	
7.00-8.45	Breakfast
9.00-9.30	Irbard Ibrahim: The Role of African Governments, Civil Society and the Clergy in the fight against Terrorism on the Continent
9.30-10.00	Amb. Martin Kimani : "State and Non-State actors and violence" A case study of Kenya
10.00-10.15	Plenary
10.15-10.30	Break
10.30-10.55	Prof. Womack Deanna: Discourses of Insecurity: American Political and Religious perceptions of Global Islam

10.55-11.20	Dr.AbdulkadirHashim: Taming Terrorism: State Policies and Muslim Grievances in Kenya
11.20-11.45	Dr. John Ndavula and Mr. John Mwangi: Media framing of the war on terror and its implications for human rights: The case of Garissa Terrorist Attacks
11.45-12.10	Dr. Damaris Parsitau: Engaging Youth for a Sustainable Culture of Peace and Security in Kenya: The role of Faith Based organizations
12.10-12.30	Dr.Twase – MungawaChidongo: Religious Encounter in African Schools: Can it be a platform for addressing Insecurity?
12.30-2.00	Lunch Break
	Practitioners Round Table
2.00-2.45	Ms Maureen Ong’ombe, Mrs Beatrice Nzovu, AbdullahiHalakhe, Mr. Mohamed Amin, IrbardIbrahim,Dr. Damaris Parsitau
2.45-3.15	Recap, Conclusion: Harold Miller:
3.15-3.40	Closing of the conference & Vote of Thanks Presentation of Gifts Visit to the Westgate Mall-Optional
Friday, 8 July 2016	
Departures	

FINANCIAL REPORT Faiths and (in) Security Conference:

Below is a narrative of the grants received and how the money was spent.

Grants Received

INCOME

I	Emory-Candler	2,068,283.00
III	EMW	473,000.00
III	Danmission	199,000.00
IV	PROCMURA	47,370.00
V	KAS	52,000.00
	Mini-Totals	<u>2,839,653.00</u>

Expenditure Report

		Income (ksh.)	Expenditure
		2,839,653.00	
I.	Youth Summit (Faiths Security Seminar)		105,682.00
2.	Transportation & Airfare		201,500.00
3.	Welcome Reception Dinner		36,000.00
4.	Hired Sound System		30,000.00
5.	Publicity (Banner, Program, Nametags)		87,450.00
6.	Communications strategy implementation team		100,000.00
7.	Media (TV Coverage)		100,000.00
8.	Stationery (files/pens/notebooks)		10,000.00
9.	Conference Crew (Rappateours & Assistants)		168,000.00
10.	Gifts for Chief Guests		75,000.00
11.	Honorarium		80,000.00
12.	Accommodation (Participants boarding & lodging)		1,333,200.00
13.	Administrative costs(Secretariat &Registration fees)		100,000.00
	Sub-Total		<u>2,426,832.00</u>
	Balance (<i>Conference Documentation Handbook</i>)		<u>412,821.00</u>
	Grand Total	<u>2,839,653.00</u>	<u>2,839,653.00</u>

POST CONFERENCE ACTIVITIES

Media Engagement

The CCMRE 'Faith and (in) Security In Africa Conference'

- Interviews & TV news coverage:
 - KTN 'The Last Word'. Interview with Prof. Mombo and Dr. Wandera. *Find link.* https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q3_3uROgrng
 - Good morning Kenya KBC. Interview with Dr. Wandera. *Find link.* https://youtu.be/Q3_3uROgrng
 - K24 News story - <https://youtu.be/0CpBQP3INOc>
- Print & online media:
 - Saturday Nation Oped by Dr. Murunga. <https://t.co/RW7EaOLIRa>
 - Feature on Platform Kenya August 2016 Edition. (prominent legal monthly publication)
 - The Star Newspaper. Find see link. http://www.the-star.co.ke/news/2016/07/09/envoy-calls-for-ways-to-end-terror-attacks_c1382284?platform=hootsuite
 - KBCTV blog mention. See link. <https://t.co/HV2A7CwfRe>
- Social media:
 - real-time highlight updates on twitter, facebook as well as post conference messaging.
 - -facebook: <https://m.facebook.com/Centre-for-Christian-Muslim-Relations-in-Eastleigh-CCMRE-1582421525357773/>
 - -twitter: @ccmreonline
 - YouTube : ccmre online - repository of interviews with conference speakers (with consented)

Note the continued digital legacy of the coverage.

CCMRE ACTIVITIES IN 2016-2017.

REFLECTIONS ON 2017 KENYAN ELECTIONS: A PANEL DISCUSSION

Prof. Esther Mombo, Dr. John Ndavula, Hon. Yussuf Hassan, Beatrice Ndzovu, Prof. Macharia Munene, Maureen Ongombe

Venue: Main Auditorium, St. Paul's University; Date: March 2, 2017 Time: 9 am to 12.30 am.

On August 8, 2014, Kenyans voted in the first election under the new 2010 constitution that sought to address numerous causes of the post-election violence in 2008. Against a background of heated discourse around “free and fair elections,” the 2017 presidential elections promise to be as closely contested and polarizing as the controversial 2007 elections. The election is generating anxiety among Kenyans and the neighboring states.

The two leading political coalitions are: the National Super Alliance (NASA) led by Raila Odinga, Kalonzo Musyoka, Moses Wetangula and Musalia Mudavadi, among others and JUBILEE led by Uhuru Kenyatta and William Ruto. These two popular coalitions are appealing largely to ethnic and elite dynamics to mobilize voters.

This panel discussion focused on historical junctures and evolving contemporary events that may have an impact on the outcome of the 2017 elections. The panel discussed Kenya's tumultuous political history and the place of the 2017 elections within that history, the interactions between ethnicity and elections in Kenya and the impact of elections on socio-political and economic developments in Kenya and the wider region. The panelists reflected on how faith communities in Kenya can play positive roles towards free, fair and peaceful elections.

Speakers:

Prof. Esther Mombo:-	Director of International Affairs and Alumni, Faculty of Theology, St Paul's University
Hon. Yussuf Hassan:-	MP Kamukunji, Nairobi
Dr. John Ndavula:-	Faculty of Communication, St. Paul's University
Beatrice Ndzovu:-	Manager, Kenya Programme, Life and Peace Institute
Prof. Macharia Munene: -	Department of International Relations and Political science, United States International University
Maureen Ongombe:-	Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh, St. Paul's University

Dr. Halkano Wario:-

Senior Research Fellow, Volkswagen Foundation, Department of History,
Religious Studies, Egerton University

Repertoire:

Rev. Van Es

Canada Consultation on Faiths and (in) Security Conference

Dr. Joseph Wandera Coordinator, CCMRE office, hosts Mr. Matheu Roy, First Secretary Canadian High Commission to Kenya and Sarah Lozowzski, Senior Analyst, Global Issues Division, Government of Canada on June 10, 2016 at St. Paul's University mini-boardroom to discuss the upcoming conference on "Faiths and (in)Security in Africa," Radicalization and the Daadab Refugee Situation. They were joined by colleagues, John Mwangi (Department of Peace and Conflict Studies), Loise Macharia (Department of Communication) and Nelly Murugi (Faculty of Theology).

Centre for Christian Muslim Relations in Eastleigh, Coordinator Joseph Wandera, on KBC's *Good Morning Kenya*, consulting on issues of Religion and Security.

Mennonite Consultation on our work in Eastleigh

Dr. Joseph Wandera shared his insights on the role of Centre for Christian Muslim Relations in Eastleigh with networks and partners at Amani Gardens, Westlands April 3, 2017.

Sudan Cultural Festival

(From left) Prof. Esther Mombo and H.E. Elasadig Abdalla Elias (Ambassador of Sudan to Kenya) meet ahead of the Sudan cultural festival in March, 2017

Prof. Esther Mombo welcomes the Sudan Ambassador to Kenya Elsadig Abdalla Elias and his delegation to St. Paul's University, Limuru at the Sudan Cultural Festival in April, 2017

Cementing relationships; Ambassador Elias plants a tree at the University Entrance.

Sudan Cultural Dances entertain with Sudanese music St Paul's University staff and Faculty at the Festival.

Students and staff of the MA Islam and Christian-Muslim Relations during a visit to the Oromo Mosque Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh - CCMRE.

St Paul's University MA Islam & Christian Muslim Relations Students and youth from Eastleigh working on the Mapping Eastleigh Project at the Eastleigh Centre offices.

(From Left) The Chair CCMRE Prof. Esther Mombo, Maureen Ong'ombe, Project Manager, Kamukunji MP-Hon. Yussuf Hassan, [Life and Peace Institute's](#) Beatrice kizi-Ndzovu, Jody Henderson at a breakfast meeting on community engagements during the 'Exploring Peaceful Coexistence in Nairobi's urban settlements in Eastleigh, Majengo and Mlango Kubwa' project and future engagements .

Training on Conflict sensitive approaches and conflict analysis training by CCMRE/LPI in April 2016

Maureen Ong'ombe, CCMRE Project Manager, makes a presentation on the findings of 'Exploring Peaceful Co-existence in Kamukunji Sub-county' at Jumuiya Country Home and Conference Centre on December 7, 2015.

Delegates make their contributions to the presentations on the research 'Exploring Peaceful Co-existence in Kamukunji Sub-county' at Jumuia Country Home and Conference Centre on December 7, 2015

World Council of Churches Visit

The Vice Chancellor Prof. Galgalo, St. Paul's University and the Chair of Centre for Christian Muslim Relations in Eastleigh Prof. Esther Mombo, the outgoing CCMRE coordinator Rt. Rev. Joseph Wandera and incoming coordinator Scholar Kiilu take a picture along World Council of Churches delegation visit at St. Paul's University, Limuru in September 2017.

WCC delegates and students follow the Panel Discussion on 'Interfaith Engagement in Post Election Contexts' in September 2017

A first year student contributes to the 'Interfaith Engagement in Post Election Contexts' discussion at the University's Amphitheatre during the WCC visit.

Christian Muslim Relations Workshop September 10th-15th at ACK St Julian's, Limuru

Introduction

We would like to take this opportunity to specially thank EMW and The Mennonite Centre, Nairobi for the grants that made the Workshop possible. The report sets out the way that the Course was run and lists those who were involved in it as facilitators and participants. The course went well and we were encouraged, by those who participated, to plan for follow-up courses to further equip them in gaining an understanding of Islam.

Purpose of the Course:

The Course acts as an Introduction to Islam, and is planned among a series of Annual Courses, each building on the previous volume. The expectation is that participants would already have had some previous exposure to Islam and have a desire to learn more about Islam, in order to be more effective in ministry.

Those who were invited were Church Leaders, both Lay and Ordained with a gender and denominational balance.

There were about 12 participants 5 ladies and 7 gentlemen.

Facilitators included Canon Francis Omondi and below Rev. Jacqueline Hoover

Rev. Jacqueline Hoover is an ordained minister in the Mennonite Church and a free-lance instructor in Islamic Studies who has lived in the Middle East for almost 20 years and now resides in the United Kingdom. She teaches overviews of the Islamic tradition and has special interests in the history of Muslim-Christian relations, Islam in sub-Saharan Africa, and Islam and gender. She is a Teaching Affiliate at the University of Nottingham and teaches regularly in Egypt, Germany, and the USA. She has also given seminars and taught courses in the Gambia, Nigeria, Lebanon, Sudan, Switzerland, and Tanzania.”

From Left-Pastors Dickson Osundwa, Joyce Shami and Jeremiah Musah among others at the Christian Muslim Relations Workshop in September 2017.

Participants of the Christian Muslim Relations Workshop enjoy a cup of tea in the evening after a day's training.

[Dr Georgina Jadim](#) visited CCMRE, at St Paul's University, Limuru to speak on "*Scriptural Reasoning & Christian Muslim Relations - Building Pathways to Peace In Times Of Trouble*"

Contribution to Public Scholarship Through Media

Peter C. & Wandera J. *Mapping Eastleigh for Christian-Muslim Relations*. Oxford: African Books Collective, 2013. *Project MUSE*, Available at <https://muse.jhu.edu/book/25186>

Life & Peace institute & Centre for Christian Muslim Relations (2016) *Exploring Peaceful Co-existence in Nairobi's Urban Settlements*. © Life & Peace Institute 2016 Centre for Christian-Muslim Relations in Eastleigh KPH, Trycksaksbolaget AB: Available http://life-peace.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/Kenya_Peaceful-Coexistence.pdf

Abdulkader T. Wandera J Ed. (2010) *Constitutional Review in Kenya and Kadhis Courts* http://www.cci.uct.ac.za/usr/cci/news/big/Limuru_Kenya_Papers.pdf

Since 2016, the coordinator has been contributing to lead opinion articles on the nexus between religion and public life. These have featured in the Daily Nation, Kenya's leading newspaper.

- Wandera Joseph. *Need for a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between religion and public life*. Daily Nation Monday 29, 2016.

<http://www.nation.co.ke/oped/Opinion/more-nuanced-understanding-relationship-religion-public-life/440808-3362128-bu60ysz/>

- Wandera, Joseph. *Scrutinize religion's role in reforms*. Daily Nation, Tuesday August 30, 2016.
- Wandera, Joseph. *Pay attention to religious diversity in Schools, Colleges*. Saturday Nation, October 8, 2016. http://www.ipsos.co.ke/NEWBASE_EXPORTS/Education%20-%20TWAVEZA/I61008_Saturday%20Nation_33_be87b.pdf
- Wandera, Joseph. *City Cathedral's centenary and a legacy of struggle for civil rights*. Daily Nation, Thursday February 16 2017. <http://www.nation.co.ke/oped/Opinion/cathedral-centenary-legacy-of-struggle-civil-rights/440808-3814336-qv9hfrz/>
- Wandera, Joseph. *We have a duty to prepare young generation for the future world*. Daily Nation, Tuesday October 11, 2016.
- Wandera, Joseph. *Vet faith leaders before they give us new IEBC bosses*. Platform, September, 2016, Number 22.
- Wandera, Joseph. *For national renewal, let's teach our youth to reject old order, and care for the weak*. The Platform, October 2016, Number 23.
- Wandera, Joseph. *Remembering All Saints in the Struggle for Democracy*. The Nairobi Law Monthly, March 2017 <http://nairobi.lawmonthly.com/index.php/2017/03/03/remembering-all-saints-cathedral-in-the-struggle-for-democracy/>
- Wandera, Joseph. *Eastleigh executions a blot on Kenya's civil rights agenda*. The Star, Saturday/Sunday 8-9 April 2017. http://www.the-star.co.ke/news/2017/04/08/eastleigh-executions-a-blot-on-kenyas-civil-rights-agenda_cI53946I#disqus_thread
- Wandera, Joseph. *London attack a call to reflect on our strategy in Somalia*. Nairobi Law Monthly, Vol 9 Issue No.4 April 20, 2017. <http://nairobi.lawmonthly.com/index.php/2017/04/20/london-attack-a-call-to-reflect-on-our-strategy-in-somalia/>

- Wandera, Joseph. *How Religious Leaders can ensure peaceful elections*. The Standard, Saturday, May 13, 2017. <https://www.standardmedia.co.ke/article/2001239498/how-religious-leaders-can-ensure-peaceful-elections>

Upcoming Consultation Projects Dr Halkano

Promise and Peril of Fighting Terrorists on Paper: Bills, Strategic Plans, Papers, Programmes of CVE in Kenya

Specialized Workshop on Critical Analysis and Survey of (Para) Legal Apparatuses in Countering Violent Extremist in Kenya

Across the world, the war on terrorism had elicited varied responses to counter such crimes. The rush to pass legislation to prevent and counter violent extremism is based on belief that terrorism is a special category of crime that cannot effectively be addressed by existing criminal laws in sovereign countries. In developing countries, the pressure to pass such bills is exerted by external western donors. The actual implementation of such bills has elicited critical responses from human right activists and civil society in general. In Kenya, a series of legislative bills was debated and passed, culminating in a general security bill. In addition to this, there have been other subsidiary strategic plans intended to counter and prevent emerging youth radicalisation, recruitment into militant groups, counter-radicalization, de-radicalization and re-integration of ex-militants into civilian population. These strategic papers and plans have been debated at both national and devolved government levels. At national level, specialized state security agencies such as the National Centre for Counter-Terrorism have published a strategic plan. At the county level, devolved governments in the coastal region have witnessed heightened youth radicalization, youth recruitment into militancy and incidences of violent extremism threatening their own strategies in CVE programmes. In addition, a number of national and international civil organizations have either locally or at international level published policy briefs that could assist those involved in CVE programmes regarding best strategies to counter radicalization. Despite a plethora of laws, strategic plans and programmes, policy briefs, specialized workshop proceedings, training manuals for counter-radicalization, de-radicalization and re-integration, the results can best be described as an uncoordinated field that results in strategic duplication, unrealistic goals far removed from the problems being addressed and top down tendencies that fuel suspicion and indifference in target audiences.

This workshop brings together prominent actors involved in CVE programmes in Kenya, drawn from donor organizations, specialized government agencies, civil society organizations, academia and faith practitioners with the aim of candid deliberation on the state of affairs concerning CVE programmes in Kenya.

Possible legal and para-legal documents for discussion:

- Security Bill 2015 and other related national legislative bills
- National Counter-Radicalisation Strategic Paper
- Kwale/Kilifi/Mombasa CVE Strategic Plan/Programme

- Existing training manuals and programmes in CVE carried out by civil society organizations.

Objectives of the Workshop

- To survey current legal and related bills, papers and plans in national, devolved and donor-funded CVE programmes, projects and agencies.
- To examine strategic objectives and goals of above documents as tools for CVE programmes.
- To discuss actual operationalization of these plans, papers, bills, programmes in field of P/CVE in urban/rural settings in Kenya.
- To deliberate on possible strengths, weaknesses and duplications of existing documents in the CVE projects.
- To compare texts in CVE programmes in Kenya with those in the region and across the global for comparative borrowing.

Changes within CCMRE

The coordinator Dr Joseph Wandera was recently appointed the Bishop of Mumias Diocese. He will be succeeded by

Ven. Scholar Wayua

Scholar holds a BA (Hons) In Divinity and MA in Islam Christian-Muslim Relations (ICMR) from St Paul's University. She is also currently a PhD Candidate at the same university with research interests in Inter-Religious dialogue and practical Theology.

Scholar lives in Kenya and is lecturing at St. Paul's University; Faculty of Theology; Department of Mission, Religion and Practical Theology and is currently coordinating CCMRE in the University. She is also an archdeacon with the Anglican Church of Kenya and participates in training of different departments. She is married and has two children.

Outgoing CCMRE Coordinator Dr Wandera...

Rt. Rev. Dr Joseph Wandera at the consecration and enthronement on September 3, 2017 in Mumias alongside are ACK clergy.

